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Master Thesis Internship

MSc Sustainable Business and Innovation

An Exploratory Study On An Innovative Sustainability Measurement System In The Leather Supply Chain

A New Approach for Capturing the Hidden Costs of Product Innovation

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Abstract

The overall purpose of this master thesis is to challenge traditional methods of measuring sustainability, transitioning performance measurement systems from qualitative to quantitative. This research was conducted at EMMA Safety Footwear (EMMASF) in The Netherlands with the intention to define how a cost based assessment could add value to the sustainability performance of a leather safety shoe under the designation of the three P's: Planet, People, and Prosperity. This was done by comparing supply chain alternative performance measurement systems across five supply chains; (1) Conventional, (2) Circular, (3) BRIC, (4) EU and (5) New Markets. The design of this pilot study is a two part case study; the first part analyses the current measurement practises employed at EMMASF, while the second part is an embedded pilot study which applies a new and innovative quantitative method, the Oiconomy Standard. The major findings as a result of the analysis was, firstly, this quantitative method brings to light the fact that because the company used all the same materials and production processes of their conventional shoes to develop a circular shoe, there is fundamentally no difference between their conventional supply chain and their circular supply chain. Secondly, it becomes evident that while some values like the emissions for transport over long distances will be more difficult to change, other issues like improving wages and labour conditions is essentially dependent on the relationship between producer and supplier. Conclusively, the Oiconomy Standard gives a realistic view of the three P's issues, by quantifying the necessary measures needed to reduce negative environmental and social impacts in the leather supply chain.

Key words: Oiconomy Standard, Eco Social Cost Unit, Leather Supply Chain, Cradle to Cradle, Circularity, Sustainable Supply Chain Management, Preventative Costs

Preface

The idea for this research stemmed from my personal interest in the leather supply chain. I am the Sustainability Manager at Goosecraft, a premium Dutch leather brand, where I drive forward due diligence in the supply chain, primarily in relation to chemical and water management. Further, with more than 15 years of experience in sustainable fashion and textiles, I realized that there was very little accountability for the use of leather in the apparel and fashion industry. In terms of sustainability, how can the industry quantify the environmental and social impact of the leather supply chain? As the apparel and fashion industry moves forward with increasing options to evaluate due diligence in its supply chain, I wanted to research how leather products can be evaluated and which performance measurement systems can be used to calculate the true costs of sustainability.

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List of Abbreviations

BRIC	Brazil Russia India China
C2C	Cradle to Cradle
CE	Circle Economy
CS	Corporate Sustainability
CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
EMMASF	Emma Safety Footwear
ESCU	Eco Social Cost Unit
LCA	Life Cycle Analysis
LWG	Leather Working Group
MDG	Millennium Development Goals
MSDS	Material Safety Data Sheet
OS	Oiconomy Standard
PDS	Product Data Sheet
PPP	People Planet Prosperity
PU	Polyurethane
SD	Sustainable Development
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SSCM	Sustainable Supply Chain Management
UN	United Nations
WBCSD	World Business Council for Sustainable Development (WBCSD)

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1. Introduction

Since the turn of the 20th century academics have stressed the necessity for businesses to go beyond making profit. In the last decade, Sustainability has fast become the catchphrase to describe future strategies within businesses. It is a hot topic among businesses, government and non-profit organisations (Crews, 2010). Witjes and Vermeulen (2015) explain that Corporate Sustainability (CS) requires an analysis of the physical dynamics inside the specific company in relation to its full physical product life cycle, as well as an analysis of the social dynamics. Both dynamics need to be addressed inside and outside the specific company. According to the World Business Council for Sustainable Development (WBCSD), Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) can be described as, “The commitment of business to contribute to sustainable economic development, working with employees, their families and the local communities” (WBCSD, 2001). One of the key challenges is to use valid and meaningful data on sustainability performance. This study will apply new developments in measuring sustainability performance in the leather supply chain, with a purpose to create a learning platform for current debates on measuring sustainability performance.

The Brundtland Commission (World Commission on Environment and Development, United Nations, 1987) first introduced the term ‘sustainability’ in their report, ‘Our Common Future’, stating that ‘Humanity has the ability to make development sustainable to ensure that it meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their needs’ (Crews, 2010). The Brundtland Report suggested the need for sustainable solutions, realizing the need for synergy between economic growth and environmental protection, concluding that even though economic growth was necessary, modifications should be made from ‘development’ to ‘sustainable development’ to achieve that growth (Doppelt, 2003).

In 2000, the United Nations (UN) member states set up a 15-year plan to ensure progress on poverty, education, health, hunger and the environment. In 2015, these eight millennium development goals (MDG’s) were replaced by the 17 sustainable development goals (SDG’s). The SDG’s include new areas such as climate change, economic inequality, innovation, and sustainable consumption amongst others. The goals are interconnected with the vision that solving one issue will in turn involve tackling other issues. Hence the SDG’s applies a full systems approach and responsibility towards all issues within a production system. With effect the goal for 2030 is that UN member states will be expected to implement these collective goals and markers to frame their political and economic policies, which will eventually impact global economies and businesses. In the last four decades, ‘sustainability’ has been interpreted to mean many different things in business and is a highly biased issue, depending on the perspective of the literature being analysed. Business leaders have been suspicious about whether it is just another management fad or a concept that will eventually change the way we do business (Crews, 2010).

Business development in sustainability regard, “(1) develop systems and tools for Life Cycle Analysis; (2) gather measurements from social and ecological impact analysis and report results to stakeholders; and (3) create an understanding and a commitment within the company and among co-operating partners throughout the value chain on a global basis (Tollin and Vej, 2012: 10)”, as essential to improving

sustainability practices. This approach is essential to make the step from the traditional linear economic model into a circular one, commonly known as 'cradle to cradle' design, popularized by design experts McDonough and Braungart (McDonough and Braungart, 2002) a theory that eliminates the concept of waste by designing goods that will still be beneficial when the product is not used for the purpose it was originally designed for, creating closed-loop cycles (Doppelt, 2003). Furthermore, a rapidly growing societal concern exacerbates the immediate need for companies to incorporate innovative performance measurement systems within their supply chains.

Sustainability as defined by the triple bottom line brings challenges to traditional measures of success, namely; profit (Milne and Gray, 2013). The triple bottom line is referred to as the three P's: "people, profits, and planet." However, the three P's can also be referred to as "people, planet and prosperity" where the third P (prosperity), reflects the developmental goal at society level in the concept of sustainable development and requires a well-functioning societal system (Witjes and Vermeulen, 2015), where companies create shared value and prosperity in the communities they serve. Subsequently, the initiation of the idea of sustainable development in the 1980's, the private sector has been steadily transitioning from the narrow concept of economic accountability to a more holistic perspective that attempts to balance economic objectives with environmental issues and growing societal expectations (Crews, 2010). In this context, sustainability includes our ecosystems, infrastructures, political institutions, education and skills. To holistically attain a state of strong sustainability, maintaining economic processes in relation to maintaining ecological systems must be viewed as complimentary to each other.

According to Fichtenbauer (2015: 4), "The solution lies in the principle of shared value, which involves creating economic value in a way that also creates value for society by addressing its needs and challenges. Businesses must reconnect company success with social progress". Shared value (Porter & Kramer, 2015) is not social responsibility, philanthropy, or even sustainability, but a new way to achieve economic success." Reap et al (2008) states however, that there are no comprehensive standards for the measurement and verification of comparative 'product' sustainability, nor for defining the functional unit and scope, the choice of impact categories and the system boundaries. This paper concentrates on the leather supply chain, with special focus on the leather safety shoe. The objective is to demonstrate how its detrimental environmental and social impacts along the value chain can be curbed with the application of a fully integrated performance measurement system. The aim of this exploration thesis is therefore to answer the research question :

"How can the application of a quantitative performance measurement system, lead to a valid cost-benefit analysis, to improve the sustainability performance of the product (leather safety shoe) through comparing supply chain alternatives?"

To ascertain the validity of such an application in a specific industrial context, related to a specific product, in a supply chain with a specific buyer, it imperative to first establish the current assessment method applied by the producer. Therefore, the following sub-question will direct this research:

- *What performance measurement system approaches are being currently employed by the producer?*

The structure of this research is as follows. The second chapter will outline a theoretical framework, which will explain the abovementioned theories in detail. This implies the specific form of Sustainable Development and Corporate Sustainability, Sustainable Supply Chain Management, Circularity in the Supply Chain and Performance Measurement Systems, calling for a fully integrated product assessment. The third chapter will present the proposed methodology to answer the sub-question and eventually the research question. The fourth chapter outlines the results by introducing the company and its product, reviewing the company's current monitoring practises, applying a new method to assess specific aspects of PPP along the company's supply chain, and finally providing a comparison between the current practises to measure sustainability and a new innovative method to measure sustainability. The fifth chapter will present the analysis and discussion. Chapter six will present recommendations to the company, the industry at large and further scientific research. Finally, chapter seven will provide the overall conclusions of this research thesis.

2. Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework is a combination of various fields of study. To answer the research question, this paper will study the theories of Corporate Sustainability, Sustainable Supply Chain Management, Circularity in the Supply Chain and Performance Measurement Systems.

2.1. Sustainable Development & Corporate Sustainability

According to the Oxford Dictionary, the word “sustainable” is an adjective, meaning “able to be maintained at a certain rate or level”. The terms ‘sustainability’ and ‘sustainable’ appeared for the first time in the Oxford English Dictionary during the second half of the 20th century, with equivalent term in French (*durable*), German (*Nachhaltigkeit*) and on in Dutch (*duurzaam*) (Pisani, 2006). The demand for raw materials and its impact on the environment are evident throughout history. Deforestation and damage to soil fertility occurred as early ancient Egyptian civilizations, due to human activities such as farming and mining but population growth, increase in consumption after the Industrial Revolution and the depletion of crucial resources boosted the awareness of the need to use resources in a sustainable way (Pisani, 2006). Sustainability can be argued as living in material comfort but within the means of nature drawing from a “stock of resources replenished by natural processes and by the sun and unquestioned diminution of which leaves future generations worse off” (Milne and Gray, 2013: 16). Furthermore, the definition of corporate sustainability differs vastly in academic circles. Dyllick and Hockerts (2002, p. 131) define CS as “meeting the needs of the firm's direct and indirect stakeholders (such as shareholders, employees, clients, pressure groups, communities, etc.), without compromising its ability to meet future stakeholder needs as well”.

Traditionally the concept of a business is an economic entity with its main responsibility as producing goods and providing services as efficiently as possible (Jamali, 2006). Conversely, however, this concept has also brought about confrontational matters such as sustaining the earth’s environment, irregular variability in commerce and finance and a larger inequality across nations (Wilkinson and Mangalagiu, 2011). From the 1980’s onwards, the private sector has been attempting to shift its business strategies from that of pure economic progress to that which encompasses a wider view and considers changing societal and environmental needs (Tollin & Vej, 2012), leading to the concept of the term ‘Triple Bottom Line’ which for business purposes refers to the three P’s: “people, profits, and planet” (Crews, 2010). In theory, the triple bottom addresses the need to implement sustainable strategy solutions ranging from population, agriculture, industry and many more to create balance between economic growth and environmental protection (Pisani, 2006). Vermeulen (2018) remarks that there is still a division between a critical and the neo-liberal approach which subscribes to a neo-liberal economic agenda, of economic growth, capital investment, and export-stability. According to van Marrewijk (2003) Corporate Sustainability is defined as “demonstrating the inclusion of social and environmental concerns in business operations and in interactions with stakeholders. This includes the social impacts in the full product life cycle and the appropriateness of the economic practices in the transactions with various

stakeholders throughout the value chain. Stakeholder theory argues that businesses have a certain responsibility to their internal and external stakeholders, meaning that they have a responsibility to individuals and groups from within as well as outside the firm (Freeman, 1984). The requirements of these internal and external stakeholders are addressed through corporate sustainability because this can determine their image and reputation, employee motivation, improved competitiveness and reduced risk (Searcy, 2012).

While corporate sustainability has a strong history in business administration through stakeholder engagement, Visser (2010) argues that corporate sustainability as a business, governance and ethics system has failed society and the environment. Visser (2010) discusses the need for a new kind of corporate sustainability that is built on a systems approach based on five principles (creativity, scalability, responsiveness, glocality and circularity) and forms the basis for a new model of responsible business, built around the four elements of value creation, good governance, societal contribution and environmental integrity. Likewise, the approach of the WBCSD is that “Corporate Social Responsibility helps companies live up to their responsibilities as global citizens and local neighbours in a fast-changing world. And acting in a socially responsible manner is more than just an ethical duty for a company, but is something that actually has a bottom line pay-off.” (WBCSD, 2018)

“Defining sustainability as the progressive maintenance of the life-supporting capacities of the planet’s ecosystems requires the subordination of traditional economic criteria to criteria based on social and ecological values, and this raises the question of whether business decision makers operating within the constraints of a capitalist system are capable of making sacrifices of profit to protect resources and ecosystems for future generations and other species” (Milne and Gray, 2013:16). Sustainability as a concept has recently been focusing on the holistic integration of a triple bottom line in business, resulting in a balancing act to seek mutual gain (Crews, 2010).

Witjes et al (2017) state a growing societal awareness of the environmental and social impact of businesses. This has increased the pressure for business to address corporate sustainability but at the same time Milne & Gray (2013) deliberates about how businesses can contribute to the this growing evolution in sustainability. Elkington’s (1997) ‘Triple Bottom Line’ principle designates accountability of People, Planet and Profit (PPP), where People represents the social dimension, Planet the environmental dimension and Profit the economic dimension. Conversely, the 2002 World Summit on Sustainable Development saw academics proposing the last ‘P’ for profit to be changed to Prosperity. According to scholars (Vermeulen, 2018; Heijungs et al., 2010), incorporating a society perspective reflects more than only the firm’s economic profit because individual firms’ profits can never serve as intended *end-outcomes* of the process towards sustainable development (Vermeulen, 2018). This in turn soundly aligns with the United Nations’ (UN) Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Therefore this research follows the *PPP approach of People, Planet and Prosperity*. This model below¹ is the result of extensive literature review and integrates “the rough consensus in global scholarly practices of sustainability assessment and the 17 UN SDGs”, (Vermeulen, 2018, p. 24.). It gives an overview of the key components of SD and offers a way to balance the three SD pillars in line with the SDGs.

¹ Figure 1

Figure 1. Integrating the rough consensus in global scholarly practices of sustainability assessment and the 17 United Nations Sustainable development goals, (Vermeulen, 2018).

2.2. Sustainable Supply Chain Management (SSCM)

During the last several decades, the private sector as well as consumers (Sheth et al., 2011) have been viewed as one of the principle causes of environmental, social and economic degradation, where businesses are perceived to be flourishing at the expense of less prosperous populations. Post World War II, rapid population growth, pollution and resource depletion posed to the environment became an evident threat and from the 1960's onwards, awareness with regards to the damage being caused to the

natural environment by human activities became widely publicized (Pisani, 2006) and “this alarmist mood, in expectation of an imminent ecological catastrophe, stimulated a new mode of thinking about development and prepared the way for sustainable development as an alternative to unlimited economic growth (Pisani, 2006: 89). In conjunction with the onset of panic that economic growth might endanger humanity, a green movement was born in 1970, represented by the first environmental non-governmental organizations like Greenpeace and Friends of the Earth, creating green political parties and developing an ideology on ecologism (Pisani, 2006).

“Our current economic system is fundamentally linear in nature. It focuses on producing products and delivering them to the customer in the fastest and cheapest way possible. We extract resources from the Earth’s surface, turn them into goods, and then discharge back into nature the by-products of this process as massive amounts of often highly toxic molecularised waste (which we call air, water, and soil pollution) or as solid, industrial, and hazardous waste (which we dispose of in landfills or burn in incinerators). After 200 years, this so-called “cradle to grave” production system has become firmly embedded in our psyches as the dominant paradigm (Doppelt, 2003:2)”. Environmental degradation such as deforestation and overfishing resulted in the concept of the environmental footprint. Osland (2003) explains environmental footprint as ‘developed countries require greater per capita material and energy flows, and therefore greater land surface, than do developing countries. The per capita effect on the earth’s crust is greatest in the wealthiest countries that extract resources at a far greater rate than they can be replaced. The globalisation of materially affluent lifestyles promulgated by the media and increased travel intensifies the demand for extracted materials.’ With the intensification of globalisation, comes the rise of exported goods, which results in the depletion of natural resources.

Since the Industrial Revolution, there has been an exponential growth in production and consumption, creating a boom in economic growth thereby increasing the quantity of manufacturing production (Pisani, 2006). This economic growth is directly related to the current day sustainability problems created by massive consumption of natural resources. Businesses view sustainable supply chain management as a key practise component to address the growing environmental and social problems incurred (Diabat et al., 2014). While Fayet & Vermeulen,(2012) state that sustainable supply chain management (SSCM) coordinates the demand for environmental and social friendly practices throughout the supply chain; Kuik (et al., 2010, p. 662) describes SSCM as “the integration of social, economic, and environmental practices within a global supply chain that provides green products, excellent services and accurate information, sharing those benefits with all employees, shareholders, business partners and the wider community.” Moreover, Vermeulen (2015) states that businesses looking beyond tier one of the supply chain are able to see opportunities matching the triple goals of sustainability: both serving the planet and principles of fairness and responsibility and also sharing increased profit. Other literature defines SSCM as “the strategic, transparent integration and achievement of an organization’s social, environmental, and economic goals in the systemic coordination of key inter-organizational business processes for improving the long-term economic performance of the individual company and its supply chains” (Carter and Rogers (2008, p. 368). Conclusively all these definitions suggest full integration of the PPP (People, Planet, Prosperity) into the supply chain.

2.3. Circularity in the Supply Chain

The concept of circularity is increasingly prevalent in academia and has become a trend in many industries and economic models. A vast array of detrimental impacts, including water usage, ecotoxicity, textile waste and poor working conditions, are associated with the textile industry (Muthu, 2017). Visser (2010), argues that Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) alone was not successful in bringing enough positive change to the business world. As Visser states, the “fundamentally flawed design” of our old take-make-dispose linear economic model can be solved through the adoption of circularity (2010, p. 17).

Circularity requires that supply chains be (re)engineered to create a system which replaces the end of life concept with restoration, moves to renewables and away from toxic inputs and eliminates waste (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2013). In many industries, these changes can be seen in approaches such as design for reparability and recyclability (Bakker, Wever, Teoh & Clercq, 2010; Braungart, McDonough & Bollinger, 2007), takeback and recycling programs and service-based models (Witjes & Lozano, 2016). To successfully implement such principles and strategies effective sustainable supply chain management is imperative. It can be ascertained from Genovese, et al. (2017) that the integration of circular economy principles within sustainable supply chain management delivers a multiplicity of benefits, particularly from an environmental perspective.

Nonetheless, the term circular economy (CE) is becoming increasingly important in academia and is applied to many different sectors, including the apparel and textiles industry. As a new field of thought, CE is highly contested with numerous and competing definitions, while still being widely posed as alternative model of production and consumption (Reike et al., 2017). Bocken, Olivetti, Cullen, Potting and Lifset (2017) introduce the core role of CE as being the maintenance of the highest possible material utility and value while transitioning away from the conventional linear (produce-use-dispose) economy to one which is restorative. Different definitions of CE exist and while some underplay social considerations, others place greater emphasis on the social pillar of sustainability (McDonough & Braungart, 2010). From an economic standpoint scholars argue that CE is proven to be financially beneficial for businesses in the long term (Kirchherr et al., 2017). Although social and economic sustainability are beyond the scope of environmental research, it is important to consider them with respect to the triple bottom line (Brundtland, 1987).

One aspect which has received little attention in the existing SSCM literature is its link to circularity. While Hassini et al., (2012) include a recycling step based on the 3Rs (reuse, recycle and return), the authors do not fully incorporate CE principles, nor explicitly link these to SSCM. However, despite the lack of SSCM frameworks for circularity, some more recent research has begun to draw links between the two concepts. Genovese et al., (2017) found that through SSCM, circular strategies can be implemented with the result being a more sustainable supply chain. As Genovese et al., (2017, p. 355) state, “integrating the core principles of circular economy within green supply chain management can provide clear advantages from an environmental point of view.” These environmental advantages are predominantly associated with diminished volumes of virgin resources and more efficient resource use (Ghisellini, Cialani & Ulgiati, 2016).

2.4. Performance Measurement Systems

The Brundtland Report principles are that of social equity, economic growth and environmental maintenance in simultaneous progression (Doppelt, 2003), highlighting the term sustainability to incorporate the components of sustainable development for the environment, the economy, and society. Since the introduction of the term 'sustainability', the concept has ballooned to focus on three key points in business, resulting in the term, 'triple bottom line' which focuses on economic profits, social impact and the environment (Crews, 2010), encouraging the wider community would take responsibility for both the causes and the consequences of environmental damage, thereby involving a strong element of intergenerational ethics (Hammond, 2006).

Voluntary certifications and standards aimed at environmental and social sustainability in the supply chain has been continuously increasing over the last 20 years. These non-state certifications, or private governance mechanisms (Gulbrandsen, 2014), typically establish environmental and social performance standards for responsible production. They require independent third-party verification to assess the compliance of the standard. Often, a wide range of stakeholders interact and establish the rules of the governance system together (Bernstein & Cashore 2007). Vermeulen (2018) distinguishes between three common approaches to map the PPP issues: (1) voluntary sustainability initiatives in the international trade of products, (2) voluntary reporting about corporate sustainability and (3) efforts to synthesize life cycle assessment (LCA) on environmental and social aspects. Milne and Gray (2013), argue that the need to relate sustainability visions and goals to processes and performance measurements has also resulted in developing frameworks like 'LCA' (life cycle assessment) analysis, 'Cradle-to-Cradle' principles (from authors McDonough & Braungart, 2002), 'ISO 14000' (environmental guidelines) and many other tools for assessing sustainability products. The LCA is an assessment tool used to provide a life cycle focus and to increase scientific knowledge on the environmental impact of products and processes, however, seeking to achieve comprehensive sustainability measurement of specific products, the LCA has some fundamental deficiencies (Croes & Vermeulen, 2015).

Under the umbrella of Corporate Responsibility, several governmental and non-governmental organizations have developed tools to measure either environmental or social performance. O'Rourke (2014) describes these efforts as forming tools, which can be applied to product design, material selection, sourcing, manufacturing, use-phase interventions and end-of-life management. External stakeholders such as NGOs, investors, governments and consumers can use the certification as a tool to identify and support high performers, putting pressure on the whole sector (Auld & Gulbrandsen, 2010).

Allocation of damage to a product or process, defined as the functional unit, is especially difficult if the product or process has multiple functions (Reap et al., 2008, p.292). Hence, the need to capture the full performance of a supply chain calls for a standardized measurement system, in the form of prevention as innovation. The Oicconomy Standard (OS) is a model standard for the life cycle sustainability assessment of products (Croes, 2012), used to measure the environmental and social performance of products (Croes & Vermeulen (2013) and it serves as a system to measure performance along the supply chain. Croes (2012) explains that the OS uses the principles of standard financial accounting for

seeking to determine the hidden preventative costs of products at all links of the supply chain and for transferring these through the supply chain in a similar manner to standard costs.

Further, Croes (2012) explains that the “goal of this standard is to provide a normalized way of measuring and communication of (un)sustainability. In this standard (un)sustainability is expressed in a virtual monetary unit, the “ESCU” (Eco Social Cost Units). As closely as possible, the ESCU score of a product equals the hidden costs, or externalities, related to a product, the costs that should have been spent to avoid any of the damage that the product causes during its entire lifecycle. Added to the standard economic price of the product the ESCU score represents the total costs of a fully sustainable alternative for the product. The ESCU also provides a normalized means of transfer of (un)sustainability through the supply chain enabling all supply chain actors to build on each other’s data.” Therefore, the goal of certifications, such as the OS, is to enable bottom-up transfer of verified sustainability data through complex supply chains and therewith present a solution of the current top-down character of most current LCA's (Croes & Vermeulen, 2013) .

Through this literature review, it became apparent that there are some key challenges in measuring (un)sustainability through a wider PPP systems approach. Hence, the objective for this research is how a product could be quantitatively measured using foreground data, enabling value chain partners to collaborate in order to establish better due diligence and transparency in the supply chain. Thereby, integrating the sub-field of circular economy to enhance the sustainability strategies of businesses, motivated the author to conduct a case study with an embedded pilot study.

3. Methodology

This chapter describes the methods used for this research thesis. The method is a pilot case study, which gathers both qualitative and quantitative data and seeks to understand how to implement the OS method within a company. The research in this case study can contribute to answering how the full costs of unsustainability on product-level in the supply chain can be assessed.

3.1. Research Design

Yin (1984, p. 23) defines the case study research method as an empirical inquiry that investigates a contemporary phenomenon within its real-life context; when the boundaries between phenomenon and context are not clearly evident; and in which multiple sources of evidence are used. A case study is defined by Gerring (2004, p. 342) as “an intensive study of a single unit for the purpose of understanding a larger class of (similar) units”. Stake (2006) argues that a case study research serves both theoretical and practical purposes. This pilot case study has two elements, the first which partly looks at various business management and collaboration processes, and the second is a learning-by-doing experiment in which the case uses the Oiconomy Standard method to generate calculations using the foreground data provided by the actors in the supply chain as well as background data provided by international data bases. Thus, this is an embedded pilot case study with the goal to link the theoretical and methodical work to a tangible case with a purpose to:

- **Link the practices around data collection, measurement and assessment on the ground.**
- **Evaluate and calculate the difference between current products and circular products, using the current data.**

EMMASF is currently working on improving the sustainability of their products. This case study uses an innovative real life test approach to assess a leather safety shoe, design and produced by EMMASF. Capturing the performance of the supply chain comes together in this case study to work on a new business case of a sustainable product (the leather safety shoe). While this product has elements of circularity, the sustainability performance of this product needs to be assessed in the full scope of sustainability, under an integrated performance measurement system. The method this case study will use is the Oiconomy Standard (OS) to measure the full (hidden) costs of a product during its entire life-time. A case study can be used to answer questions like “why” or “how” and when it is about a contemporary phenomenon in a real-life context (Yin, 2009). The aim of this research has two purposes, (1)contributing to the development of the OS method, and (2) gain a holistic understanding of the impact of a product through in-depth analysis. Therefore a case study is considered valid for this research, which aims to go beyond theoretical formulation, investigating the applicability of a newly developed and innovative measurement system put into practice as a valid cost-benefit assessment.

3.2. The Case Study

The research is a case study with an embedded pilot, with a view on how social and environmental concerns are currently measured in the value chain. The research project examines some key elements in the production of a leather safety shoe, namely; the field of leather safety shoe production and how the company is currently undertaking production in their supply chain. The first part of this case study is to examine how this final key producer in this value chain is measuring the sustainability of a product. Further, the research will zoom in on the corporate sustainability strategy and methods the company is using to evaluate the level of their (un)sustainability in the supply chain. The second part of this case study is an embedded pilot in which the author will conduct a pilot calculation using an alternative innovative method, the Oiconomy Standard. Finally, a comparison between the current monitoring assessment used by the company and the innovative Oiconomy Standard will be provided.

LCA in principle considers the full value chain, although the system is designed in such a way that there are many boundary choices and data sets which are general and not case specific. The essence of the Oiconomy system is the step towards making these values specific with each of the suppliers, calculating their own contribution, and translating this in monetary values which in itself is not original, but the Oiconomy system focuses on prevention costs, herein making the key challenge for the pilot, how this system connects to the data available by producers in each step of the value chain to make that work. The aim of using the OS as a performance measurement system framework is to capture social and environmental compliance along the supply chain.

The issues addressed under the umbrella of CR concern wide agendas covering planet, people and prosperity (Vermeulen & Witjes, 2015) , as well as many sub-agendas such as carbon-footprinting, circularity, biodiversity and social issues, amongst many other. The focus on these sub issues are often conflicting with each other. Consequently, there is a call for an integrated approach and therefore this case will focus on specific topics for a full assessment, differentiating this research from a broad system assessment to a focused system assessment.

3.3. The Oiconomy Standard

The second part of the case study is the application of the Oiconomy Standard method to complete pilot calculations. The case study conducted for EMMASF is an exemplary pilot case study, for new methodology that is rooted in philosophies of Corporate Sustainability. This case study intends to capture the impact of a product, thereby making the move from a traditional Life Cycle Analysis (LCA) to the Oiconomy Standard Measurement Performance System. Conclusively, a full value chain analysis will be monitored.

The Oiconomy Standard method was developed on the premise that the price of a product contains hidden costs which are not accounted for. These costs can be divided into 3 phases (OS, 2012):

1. The costs of social irresponsibility and the consequent poverty, inequality and poor health-, living- or working conditions (People).

2. The costs of damage to the environment and the depletion of resources endangering the future well-being of mankind (Planet).

3. Profits obtained by irresponsible financial behaviour, criminal activities or corruption (Prosperity).

Croes (2012) states that without these hidden costs, the current prices of products do not represent their true costs, resulting in continued unsustainable production as opposed to sustainable production. In order to calculate the level of (un)sustainability of the leather safety shoe in the EMMASF supply chain, the following steps as set out by the OS will be adhered to.

The OS is a model standard developed by Croes and Vermeulen to assess the life cycle sustainability of products. The goal of this standard offers a normalized way of measuring and communicating (un)sustainability, which is expressed in a virtual monetary unit, the “ESCU” (Eco Social Cost Units). The ESCU score equals the hidden costs or externalities of the product. These are the costs that should have been spent to avoid any of the damage that the product causes during its entire lifecycle. In combination with the standard (economic) price of the product, the ESCU score represents the total costs of a fully sustainable alternative for the product (Croes, 2012). This calculation provides quantitative information, making it possible to determine how sustainable the base-line product is, and subsequently, the action that needs to occur in order to have a completely sustainable product.

The OS incorporates the principles of standard financial accounting to determine the ESCUs of a product at all links in the supply chain. This standard includes a method to verifiably transfer these sustainability data through the supply chain by means of the ESCU, enabling a specific assessment of specific products and their specific supply chains. The ESCU transfers sustainability through the supply chain, in a normalized way that allows all supply chain players to build on each other’s data (Croes, 2012). Next to that, the OS offers the possibility of third-party verification and certification in the future.

All ESCU scores are the product of a quantitative and a price factor. The measurement of the magnitude or quantity factor for each aspect (QAspect) is standardized by the criteria of this standard. The price factor (PAspect) represent the preventative costs for the aspect. Default values for these are presented in the “Oiconomy Foundation database” (O.F. database) and represent the marginal preventative costs, the highest costs of all major preventative measures that are necessary to globally reach the standard or target that has been set for the relevant aspect. Applicants shall use these default values unless, at certain conditions, they can demonstrate a lower actual value (Croes, 2012).

This “Oiconomy system” is designed to be self-learning. Where the default price factors are initially scientifically determined for the fundamental aspect categories and a series of subcategories, supply chain actors may provide data for more specific subcategories, this way demonstrating their own lower ESCU’s and updating the system for all. Suppliers of sustainability improving technology or methodologies may in this way demonstrate their contributions.

This standard enables determination and effective communication of the (un)sustainability of any product. The product may be a consumption product, a utensil, a personal service or an impersonal service. The entire product lifecycle is assessed, from cradle to grave. A great variation of aspects of sustainability (including ecological, social and economic responsibility) is considered in order to provide a balanced and comprehensive assessment of product sustainability.

This standard requires transparency of all data relevant to sustainability, prescribes the method of determination and communication and requires the organization to execute a full assessment in order to enable external stakeholders to make their own value choices between the aspects and make their own composite indicator. This standard makes no requirements to any specific aspects of sustainability, but only presents a standardized way of calculation of the (un)sustainability of a product.

3.4. Data Collection

The research conducted in this study uses theoretical implications, existing performance measurement systems, supply chain data and the Oiconomy Standard method. The data was collected in various ways starting with desktop research to create a scientific foundation of theories on Corporate Sustainability, Sustainable Supply Chain Management, Performance Measurement Systems and Circularity in the Supply Chain. Subsequently an in-depth analysis of current monitoring and product assessment practises was conducted to understand how EMMASF is working on PPP issues. General available literature on circular theories were used to substantiate C2C and CE data retrieved from interviews and personal communication at EMMASF. Interviews were informal and unstructured to allow the interviewee to speak freely which offers the prospect of flexibility and allows the researcher to change direction in the course of the investigation (Bryman, 2012). Furthermore, auxiliary meetings and conversations took place at EMMASF to capture data about the processes in their current supply chain. These personal communication are included in this research and the author has relied on this information to establish assumptions when accessing background data to calculate preventive costs. The desktop research contributed to answering the sub-question:

- **What performance measurement system approaches are being currently employed by the producer?**

To calculate the full costs of the product, supply chain data was collected. Since the author collaborated with EMMASF on this project, it was possible not only to take interviews with employees at EMMASF² but also to send out questionnaires³ to supplier partners in their supply chain via EMMASF. The OS asks for an analysis on the complete product value chain. ESCUs are allocated for five life cycle contributions: supplies, organization's own contribution, consumption, disposal and bonus ESCUs (Croes, 2012). However, it should be noted that an analysis can only be made if supplier partners are willing to participate.

Data collection focussed around the leather safety shoe produced by EMMASF. Companies who implement SSCM are inclined to look predominantly at the direct environmental impacts associated with their first-tier suppliers (Darnall, Jolley & Handfield, 2008). Such suppliers are those which deliver products directly to the brand, while second tier suppliers are those which produce inputs used in the production process of the first tier (Darnall et al. 2008). For the purposes of this research data collection

² Appendix 1

³ Appendix 2

considered: companies (both first and second tier) within the supply chain of EMMASF; their methods of production; purchasing and sales; and circularity strategies. Data will be compiled in the following phases:

- *Review of current monitoring and product assessment practices at EMMASF*
- *Review of type and quality of available triple PPP data at EMMASF*
- *Application of OS method*

In principle Oiconomy intends to address all the PPP aspects. Since the OS is still in development, and for practical and availability reasons, for this pilot, the author has reduced the number of environmental and social aspects to be calculated. This pilot does not cover all aspects of environmental and social impacts but chooses the most crucial factors relevant to the safety shoe supply chain. The OS claims to be as objective as possible by the use of preventative costs instead of a damage related indicator making it possible to objectively weigh the different aspects by their preventative costs (Croes, 2012). This standard categorizes all types of eco-social-economic aspects in the following fundamental categories:

- A. Pollution of air, water or soil.
- B. Depletion of scarce resources.
- C. Use of scarce land.
- D. Damage to biodiversity or scarce nature.
- E. Public health risks.
- F. Waste.
- G. Poverty and Economic irresponsibility.
- H. Poor Labour conditions.
- I. Corruption and violence.
- J. Various social responsibilities.

Due to scope and time constrictions, this research limits the use of OS indicators. For each 'P', a set number critical indicators are chosen based on specific measurement systems and conversations with employees at EMMASF. The categories for each 'P' are listed in the chapter 4.3 Case Study : Part 2: Applying the OS Methods to the Leather Safety Shoe. Subsequently the OS database was used to calculate the hidden costs of the product. This data-base contains a description, general data, the ESCUs and the sources for each category and indicators. By analysing supply chain data and combining this data with the information gathered during desk-research, the research question can be answered. Finally, the results of the OS are analysed and conclusions are deduced concerning the true costs of the product along the supply chain and as such, understand in what way the knowledge gained by OS could be used by the company to improve its sustainability performance in the future.

3.5. Limitations

This research considered only a limited number of materials and suppliers in the supply chain examining primarily the components leather, steel and polyurethane. These three components cover 63,29% of the total components in the Article 730 D Billy. All other components are smaller percentages of the whole but were not considered for the calculation in this research.

At the start of this investigation, it was the intention of the author to calculate all ESCU values for Polyurethane (PU), however, there was not enough information to calculate two of the Planet aspects, namely: Chemical and Waste. It should therefore be noted that these two categories for Polyurethane have been excluded from calculation. Nonetheless, EMMASF is predominantly purchasing the chemical components for moulding PU into form. These components are bought from long-time partner Covestro in Germany. Using background data from Covestro, it has been ascertained that 70% of the PU components are recycled. Using the foreground data, which states that this Article 730 D Billy contains 21,74% of PU and 70% of the PU is recycled, means that the shoe already has a 15% recycled material content. It should therefore be noted that it would be of consequence to further detail this component because PU is one of materials that already has 70% recycled material.

Other limitations include a deficiency in foreground data due to a lack of collaboration in the supply chain as well as a lack of quantitative knowledge in environmental and social sustainability, at producer level and raw materials supplier level. Further, the author was not allowed direct access to the supply chain of EMMASF and was dependent on the cooperation and speed of the employees of EMMASF. Therefore in some calculations, foreground data was substituted for background data, using international databases for environmental and social eco costs, meaning that assumptions were made based on auxiliary scientific literature on specific subject matters.

4. Results

This chapter presents the case study with an embedded pilot conducted at EMMASF, reflecting on the outcomes of the two-stage approach methodology applied in this research and the ambition of EMMASF to provide alternative sustainable solutions to safety footwear for existing and future customers. The following section examines a conventional leather safety shoe with the company's ambition to develop a circular leather safety shoe, and how EMMASF currently assesses and monitors production practices along their supply chain. The OS is applied to make a comparison between the conventional safety shoe and the circular safety shoe to evaluate how (un)sustainable the existing supply chain is. Further, three supplementary supply chains (BRIC, EU, New Markets) are included for comparison analysis.

4.1. The Case Company and Product: EMMA Safety Footwear (EMMASF)

Almost a century ago, The Dutch State Mines (DSM) decided to introduce initiatives to help former disabled miners find suitable alternative work. At the time, a specialized shoe factory, was one of these initiatives, hence, most of EMMASF's employees in the beginning were experienced former miners. At its root, EMMASF has always been a socially responsible company, and continues to provide jobs for 150 people, 80% of whom have a disability (Interview, Frans Beckers, 2017). Recently, since 2013, new management at EMMASF saw the rise of a new business strategy to include environmental sustainability by new ways of recycling old materials (Interview, Frans Beckers, 2017).

EMMASF has been deliberating new ways to improve the product design and production processes of a conventional safety shoe into a circular safety shoe, hence searching for new methods to evaluate their social and environmental footprint. Their mission is: "supply chain transparency", and their vision is: "to become an international leader in the development of circular products and processes within its sector" (Interview, Frans Beckers, 2017). Since, sustainable development is a global process, EMMASF wants her policy to be aligned with the SDGs of the United Nations. Their ambition is to incorporate the following SDG Goals: Responsible Consumption (12); Decent Work and Economic Growth (8); Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure (9); Affordable and Clean Energy (7); and Partnership for the Goals (17).

Several performance measurement systems have been developed to address the sustainability of a product and/or process. The apparel and textiles industry recognises numerous standards that address different (raw) material production, product development and manufacturing along the supply chain. Well-known standards are Solidaridad, BSCI, Fair Wear Foundation, Made-By, ZDHC and many more (The Ethical Fashion Source, 2016). Each standard focuses on different pegs along the supply chain and addresses different issues, also with different approaches. BSCI focuses on certifications for retailers while Fair Wear Foundation focuses on labour and working conditions certifications for brands. ZDHC focuses on chemical management, while Made-By focuses on wet processing facilities.

The leather supply chain has recently become a focal point for social and environmental management (Interview, Frans Tilstra, 2018), focussing on chemical and water management in tanneries. The current

prevention options in the leather industry are minimal. For the purpose of this research the most recent performance measurement assessments in the leather supply chain were evaluated, namely; Tannery of the Future and The Leather Working Group. The Tannery of the Future self-assessment tool has been designed as a guideline for tanneries. It is a basic self-assessment tool to further understanding on how individual tanneries score on the sustainability issues that end-consumers of leather products consider to be important. The tool covers a range of relevant subjects (social and environmental), but states that it is the sole responsibility of the individuals or companies using this tool to determine the status of the content covered by the tool (Tannery of the Future, 2016). It is a conditional first assessment of tanneries, and a good starting point that allows the facility to understand the scope of categories relevant and necessary for gathering internal data. The Leather Working Group (LWG) is a multi-stakeholder group, comprised of brands, retailers, leather manufacturers, chemical companies and other relevant parties in the leather supply chain. LWG's key objective is creating awareness in the leather industry and pushing forward assessment on environmental performance. LWG assesses tanners in a 2-3 day audit which includes environmental management systems, water usage, energy consumption, air emissions, effluent treatment and waste management. While Tannery of the Future opens dialogue with self-assessment and creates awareness that the leather industry must improve social and environmental practices; and LWG focuses on environmental auditing, they are both subjective management systems.

This case study uses the PPP theory as a baseline for sustainable development and corporate sustainability, so it is the mission of this research thesis, to determine how EMMASF can best reach their goals in developing a more sustainable product and production process. In order to do this, the research will focus on one safety shoe: Article 730 D Billy. This article is an all-purpose, oil, acid and water repellent boot. It is suitable for chemical, metal, construction, automotive, agriculture and oil & gas industries (Website: EMMASF). This research will assess delineated categories of this specific product and the supply chain processes.

Figure 2 below visually describes the components of a generic safety shoe, while figure 3 below visually demonstrates the article produced by EMMASF that will be assessed in this research: Article 730 D Billy. Major components of the Article 730 D Billy (Figure 3) are Leather, Polyurethane and Steel. Leather comprises 17,63%, Polyurethane 23,53% and Steel 22,13%. These three components make up 63,29% of the total components. Other significant components are polyamide 4,48% and anti-bacterial foam 3,93%. Furthermore, unknown materials account for 4,49% of the total components.

Figure 2 – Description of Generic Safety Shoe⁴

Figure 3 – Leather Safety Shoe: Article 730 D Billy

Table 1 below summarizes the components of the Article 730 D Billy⁵, into pattern designation, the component material used for said pattern designation, the weight of the component and the percentage

⁴ <https://www.pinterest.com/pin/437764026255060111/>

⁵ <https://www.emmasafetyfootwear.com/webshop/catalog/billy-zwart.html>

in relation to the whole shoe. The information is retrieved from the Article 730 D Billy product data sheets (PDS) and material safety data sheets (MSDS).

730 D Billy (781,9grams) - Material Components			
Pattern Designation	Material	Component Weight	Percentage
Vamp Counter	Leather	90 gram	11,50%
Collar, bellow tongue	Leather	48 gram	6,13%
Vamp lining, quarter lining, tongue lining	Polyamide	35 gram	4,48%
Paspel (Vivo)	Polyurethane	3 gram	0,38%
Collar sponge	Polyurethane	7 gram	0,90%
Tongue Sponge	Polyurethane	3 gram	0,38%
Non woven insole/Pamilha	Non-woven	22 gram	2,80%
Tong logo Emma	Rubber	2 gram	0,26%
Quarter logo Emma	Rubber	< 1 gram	0,13%
Upper stitching	Material unknown	< 1 gram	0,13%
Inlay sole	Anit-bacterial foam	30,7 gram	3,93%
Laces	Material unknown	6,1 gram	0,78%
Counter lining	Microfiber	< 1 gram	0,13%
Comfort Sponge	Polyurethane	< 1 gram	0,13%
Contrefort	Material unknown	10 gram	1,28%
Eyelets	Material unknown	18 gram	2,30%
Steel toecap	Steel	Neus: 98 gram	12,53%
		Strip: 5 gram	0,64%
Midsole	Polyurethane	170 gram	21,74%
Duo sole	Rubber	155 gram	19,82%
Outsole	Steel	75,1 gram	9,60%

Table 1 : Material Components Article 730 D Billy

EMMASF prides itself on quality (Interview, Ronny van der Wegen, 2018) which resulted in establishing a production location in Brazil, working with local craftsmen for their safety shoes and boots. EMMASF also works with production locations in India and China, and has supplier partners in Germany and Italy.

Using the components of the Article 730 D Billy, this research will investigate the (1) conventional supply chain at EMMASF; (2) the circular supply chain of EMMASF; a theoretical BRIC supply chain; a theoretical European Supply Chain; and a theoretical New markets supply chain.

4.2. Case Study : Part 1

REVIEW OF CURRENT MONITORING AND PRODUCT ASSESSMENT PRACTICES AT EMMASF

EMMASF employed FBBasic to initiate research (Interview, Frans Beckers, 2018) and development into designing and producing a circular safety shoe. FBBasic is a company that focuses on the regeneration of raw materials. The main focus at FBBasic is to transform linear production and consumption systems into circular systems (Bocken et al., 2016), whether or not based on the principle of C2C. This departure from the linear economy can be executed in different ways. The 3R principle is regarded as an effective means of implementing CE principles (Yang, Zhou & Xu, 2014). The 3R's refer to reduction, reuse and recycling of material inputs and these strategies are prioritised in order of their contribution towards circularity; with reduction being the most preferential strategy and recycling the least in this model. Ghisellini et al., (2016) describe the reduction principle as aiming to improve the efficiency in production processes (eco-efficiency) by minimising the input of new raw materials, energy and waste. Reuse refers to a situation in which products or components are used again to fulfil the same purpose that they were initially intended to. Third, the recycle principle deals with the recovery of waste materials by reprocessing them into new products either with the same intended use, or for a new purpose (Ghisellini et al., 2016). The model has been amended and developed with some new versions giving a greater number of 'R' strategies for closing resource loops (Potting, Hekkert, Worrell & Hanemaaijer, 2017). These more detailed models bring limitations as strategies can be overlapping and therefore harder to distinguish between and measure. Recycling is a key means of enabling circularity however it is dependent on the advancement of technology and the economic viability of recycling processes and these hinder its ability to facilitate sustainability and circularity (Löfgren & Enocson, 2014).

According to Frans Beckers, FBBasic approached EMMASF in 2015 with the idea to create a circular safety workwear shoe (Interview, Frans Beckers, 2017). Mr Beckers has worked closely with Michael Braungart and was the Benelux Managing Director for 7 years at Cradle to Cradle (C2C) Certification. Cradle-to-Cradle (McDonnough and Braungart 2002) is an holistic approach on what our socio-economic system should be, with the approach of minimizing the negative impact of our economic activities while stimulating the and optimizing the positive impact (Wever & Vogtländer, 2014). The Cradle-to-Cradle principles⁶ are:

- *Materials health, which means that materials which are used in products must be safe for use and continuous recycling. This means that they must be free of any potentially toxic substances.*
- *Materials reutilization, which means that all materials in the product must be part of continuous recycling systems.*

⁶ <https://www.c2ccertified.org/get-certified/product-certification>

- *Renewable energy, which means that 100% of the energy in the production and use phase must be renewable.*
- *Water stewardship, which means that water must be kept clean.*
- *Social fairness, which means that labour conditions must be kept at a high level.*

Frans Beckers (Interview, 2017) states that the concept of C2C was utilized as inspiration and applied eclectically. However, it should be noted that Mr. Beckers also states that in his opinion, C2C has a scientific layer which makes it a worthwhile and transparent tool to measure the circularity of a product. However, scholars critique of C2C is that it represents a technical fix, seeking solutions in technological innovations, without addressing possible solutions in our society or culture (Bakker et al, 2012). As with C2C certification, Mr. Beckers applied the first two principles, namely, Materials Health and Materials Reutilization, to evaluate the level of circularity of 4 alternative design models of workwear shoes, nevertheless, not yet in production. FBBasic requested the product data sheets (PDS) and material safety data sheets (MSDS) from all EMMA SF suppliers. If the relevant information does not appear on these data sheets, further questions to the suppliers on material content are requested. For the purpose of this research, the author was allowed to view the PDS & MSDS but not to reference it for this research as the information was deemed confidential.

The method sequence used to measure the circularity of a safety shoe at EMMA SF follows the train of thought that the products they are working with are not compared to each other in levels of more or less circular, because it depends on circumstance and application. Table 2 outlines a C2C Inspired Assessment of Article 730D Billy and the following reasoning was provided by Frans Beckers: *“We envisaged two stages, and for this stage we started to make present models and future models circular from a material health and material recuperation point of view. The next stage which we have already started we want to see whether we can use input material from other supply cycles or the supply cycles of EMMA safety shoes to add recycle content to the safety shoes amongst others. The ultimate goal is to connect supply cycles from various sectors. That is ultimate goal in the circular economy. But for this stage we concentrated on the two elements of cradle to cradle – material health and material recuperation. There one can see if a component fully complies to the material health aspect so if its fully safe, we give it an A status, if an element has to evolve in the next 5-6 years we give it a B which means low priority, if it means you have to improve the product or element within 2-3 years, then we give it a C. In c2c theory there is also the X classification, which are elements that should be replaced or improve within 12-18 months. We decided that we don’t want to have any X elements in the shoes. There is also a 5th classification and that is the ‘banned list materials’ – those materials are from a legal point of view can be used in the market, but from a health point of view we already know we should put a banned list materials in your products. So that’s the material health perspective.*

The other perspective is next use application. Are we able to give a next use application to a component or a raw material. Ultimately without losing quality or value. So for example, the leather in the shoe, from material health perspective, because it’s still chrome tanned, we should say it’s a B or a C element, because in the end of we still want to use leather for a shaft then we should use vegetable tanned leather. At the same time we know we cannot change that market overnight, it will take another 5-7

years. We need innovation time as we know that there is vegetable tanned leather in the market but not for this commercial market. So we say that as long as the market uses leather for shafts, we will go to vegetable tanned leather.

For example: on the polyamide shafts, some are pure polyamide without any finishing, that's an A label because it's a clean polyamide, and you can put it in a recycling process and the shaft can become a shaft again or plastic or a fibre for a carpet. So shoes have a polyurethane finishing on it and for that aspect we say that from a material health aspect, there is nothing wrong but from a material recuperation point, it can be improved so we give it a B from that perspective and that we have an improvement program on the element. So we try to separate the polyurethane from the polyamide so we have two raw materials or is it possible to go to a mono material so a pure polyamide but with that characteristics for which the polyurethane is used.

This procedure we did for every element. A, B, C, OR X and then a development program for every element. So that is our road map. That is the way c2c people do it as well. Then in terms of priority we made a list for every element, we put down the weight, and that is the weight impact on the shoe. Unless it's an x, then it has to be changed. For example the show label was made from PVC, from the weight perspective it is not important but because it was an X, we had to take it out. "(Interview, Frans Beckers, 2017)

Using the PDS and MSDS, each material component is weighted and allocated a percentage in relation to the total weight of the shoe. In this phase, Frans Beckers applies the first two steps of C2C, namely; (1) Materials health, which means that materials which are used in products must be safe for use and continuous recycling. This means that they must be free of any potentially toxic substances. And (2) Materials reutilisation, which means that all materials in the product must be part of continuous recycling systems. Material health is divided into A, B, C or X classification. 'A' means that it is fully recyclable; 'B' means the component needs to improve in 5-6 years; 'C' means that the component needs to be improved in 2-3 years; and 'X' means that the component should be replaced in 12-18 months. Material reutilisation refers to the next use application of the component or the raw material. The first deduction of this project to measure sustainability resulted in the following C2C inspired (Interview, Frans Beckers 2017) assessment of the components⁷.

⁷ Table 2

730 D Billy (781,9grams) - Material Components with C2C Assesment by FB Basic				
Pattern Designation	Material	Component Weight	Percentage	C2C Assesment by FB Basic
Vamp Counter	Leather	90 gram	11,50%	B
Collar, bellow tongue	Leather	48 gram	6,13%	B
Vamp lining, quarter lining, tongue lining	Polyamide	35 gram	4,48%	A
Paspel (Vivo)	Polyurethane	3 gram	0,38%	C
Collar sponge	Polyurethane	7 gram	0,90%	C
Tongue Sponge	Polyurethane	3 gram	0,38%	C
Non woven insole/Pamilha	Non-woven	22 gram	2,80%	B
Tong logo Emma	Rubber	2 gram	0,26%	X
Quarter logo Emma	Rubber	< 1 gram	0,13%	X
Upper stitching	Material unknown	< 1 gram	0,13%	A
Inlay sole	Anit-bacterial foam	30,7 gram	3,93%	B
Laces	Material unknown	6,1 gram	0,78%	B
Counter lining	Microfiber	< 1 gram	0,13%	A
Comfort Sponge	Polyurethane	< 1 gram	0,13%	C
Contrefort	Material unknown	10 gram	1,28%	C
Eyelets	Material unknown	18 gram	2,30%	A
Steel toecap	Steel	Neus: 98 gram	12,53%	A
		Strip: 5 gram	0,64%	x
Midsole	Polyurethane	170 gram	21,74%	C
Duo sole	Rubber	155 gram	19,82%	A
Outsole	Steel	75,1 gram	9,60%	A

Table 2 : Material Components Article 730 D Billy with C2C Assesment by FB Basic

The most recent outcome resulting from the above analysis⁸ of Frans Beckers is the development of a campaign on the “positive footprint”. EMMASF released a new campaign on The Positive Footprint⁹ stating their goals for PPP, stating their intention to have only a positive footprint on their production chain, develop circular products and continue in their endeavours to provide work for less abled in The

⁸ Table 2

⁹ Appendix 1, Iris van Wanrooij, EMMASF

Netherlands. EMMASF has a long history of providing jobs for the less able at their production facility Protag in Brunssum. In relation to the second 'P' for People, EMMASF has been a social enterprise since inception in 1931, and it is clear that the organisation creates opportunity for diversity and inclusiveness. However, when it comes to documentation on the first 'P' (Planet) and third 'P' (Prosperity), there is little to no information (Interview, Ronny van der Wegen, 2018) on environmental management along the supply chain or fair economic trade in less developed countries.

By observing the course of action EMMASF has recently taken to initiate a project aimed at circularity and circular economy strategies in their product development, it is evident that the company is looking for ways and means to improve sustainability in their supply chain. Hence, even though they are taking steps to implement sustainability strategies within the company, they are currently dependent on qualitative type of measuring systems and assessments, based on potential solutions rather than defining the actual performance of the leather safety shoe.

4.3. Case Study : Part 2

APPLYING THE OS METHODS TO THE LEATHER SAFETY SHOE

Safety footwear protects the wearer against a plethora of dangers. The construction of safety footwear comprises various main components, namely; toe cap, upper material, lining material, heel cap, padding, lacing, removable insoles, insoles, outsole, midsection with insert and penetration resistant insoles. In the sample Article 730 D Billy, the main components are leather for the upper material, steel for the toecap and outsole and polyurethane for the midsole and outer toecap. The manufacturing of shoes involves many different steps from raw materials to post consumer disposal. Shoe production is linear in nature, with Figure 3 describing the supply chain process from raw materials to shoe assembly at EMMASF. The raw materials are predominantly supplied by their long term partner in Brazil (Interview, Ronny van der Wegen, 2018); the chemical components to construct the outsoles and midsoles and supplied by their long term partner in Germany; the assembly is partly done in the factory of the raw materials supplier; and finally constructing the shoe into a final product is done in production facility in The Netherlands.

In principle, a company using the Oiconomy Standard would perform the steps of the calculation themselves, but since this research is a pilot study, the author has made a sample calculation of the (un)sustainability of a leather safety shoe. This sample calculation is based on a collaboration with the EMMASF, but since retrieving data from the supply chain was difficult, this research uses assumptions based on available data for those various alternatives.

Tier 4 - Raw Materials

- Animal hide, raw rubber, synthetic polymers

Tier 3 - Component Manufacturing

- Insoles, outsoles, midsoles, heels, laces

Tier 2 - Footwear Assembly

- Pattern cutting, upper cutting, sewing and closing, making and finishing

Tier 1 - Finished Product & Packaging

Figure 3 – Value Chain in EMMASF

Subsequent to mapping the supply chain at EMMASF and the supply chain at their main suppliers, it was possible to identify the most essential sustainability impacts to be included in this research. The leather supply chain is currently associated with a sundry of detrimental environmental impacts, including, water toxicity, eco toxicity, human toxicity and insufficient working conditions (Kolomaznik et al., 2008). According to organizations like the Leather Working Group, managing risk in upstream suppliers demands assurance for improvements in the following four hotspots: (1) raw material resources, (2) traceability and animal welfare, (3) labour and working conditions, and (4) chemical management (BLC Leather Tech, 2017)¹⁰. To proactively build a sustainable leather supply chain, an effective performance measurement system is dependent on transparency beyond Tier 1 manufacturing.

In the shoe manufacturing industry hazardous chemicals are found in the leather processes, rubber and plastics and the metal parts of the shoe (SGS, 2018) Chromium VI is considered to be a high risk parameter for leather footwear, because more than 85% of all leathers produced globally use chrome-based tanning technology. Phthalates are important concerns for plastic and rubber footwear. Phthalates or phthalate esters are a group of chemical compounds that are mainly used as plasticizers to increase the flexibility of plastics. For metal parts and accessories on footwear, nickel release should be strictly monitored and it is better to only use qualified metal parts after proper processing and testing.

In leather tanning processes, one of the chemicals that has the greatest environmental impact is basic chromium sulphate, a trivalent chromium salt, and the most widely used tanning agent in the leather

¹⁰ <https://www.blcleathertech.com/>

industry. When leather is processed by conventional tanning, only 54–57% of the chromium (Cr) applied reacts with the hides and skins (Kilic et al, 2011) . The rest is discharged as liquid and solid waste.

Transportation data was gathered, including transportation mode, and distance for transporting materials or goods in between the shoes' life cycle phases. For transportation of raw materials or parts to the manufacturing facility, supplier locations (by country) were obtained. Considering the volume of shipped materials and the locations of suppliers, as well as emissions factors for transport via freight ship and average truck obtained from databases such as ecoinvent, the impact of transporting raw materials could be estimated (Cheah et al, 2012).

In general, there are two main waste streams in any industry – solid waste and liquid waste. Solid waste from apparel production contains fabric cutting, thread waste, waste paper, yarn cones and tubes and packaging waste (Larney & van Aardt, 2010). However the exact waste streams are obviously dependent upon the role of the company in the supply chain. The liquid waste streams generally refer to polluted wastewater (Joy, Hickson & Buchanan, 1978). It should be noted that the waste streams do not necessarily need to be circulated within the same company or into the same product. Open-loop recycling, unlike closed-loop, involves manufacturing of the material into a different product, not the same (Haupt et al., 2016). Hence, in improving the efficiency of recycling for CE a transition to closed-loops is recommended by Haupt et al., (2016). It can also be the case that a waste stream is sent to another company for further processing and enters a new production process and supply chain.

Wages, child labour and corruption as stipulated in the SDG's address goals on societal fairness at individual human level and societal level (Vermeulen 2018). The Universal Declaration of Human Rights ¹¹(1948) recognises the worker's right to "a just and favourable remuneration ensuring for himself and his family an existence worthy of human dignity". In many developing countries, minimum wages set by the government fall far short of what many estimate to be a living wage (ETI, 2008)¹².

If the above sources are taken into consideration, there is a strong consensus that the most material topics in relation to the supply chain of this leather safety shoe can be narrowed down to be calculated into six aspects: chemicals, transport, waste, wages, child labour and corruption. Therefore, for the purpose of this pilot, the author has limited the issues that will be taken into account, but the most relevant issues in each PPP category are taken into account.

This section briefly summarises the method of data collection for the three main components of a leather safety shoe; leather vamp and counter, steel toe cap and outsole and polyurethane midsoles. This OS method is a method for companies to collect all relevant data on (un)sustainability in their supply chain. Consequently, to objectively map these data according to the costs that should have been spent on damage preventative measures and express the result in a monetary unit, the Eco Social Cost Unit (ESCU), (OS, 2012). Furthermore, the OS method, is able to transfer the given (un)sustainability data through the supply chain by means of the ESCU, enabling a specific assessment of specific products and their specific supply chains.

¹¹ <http://www.un.org/en/universal-declaration-human-rights/>

¹² <https://ethicaltrade.org/>

In order to define the ESCU'S for variable phases in the supply chain of a leather safety shoe at EMMASF, this research utilised foreground and background data. To obtain foreground data, two questionnaires¹³ were developed and distributed to suppliers of EMMASF. The first questionnaire requested quantitative data but since this was largely unavailable in several parts of the supply chain, a second questionnaire was developed to obtain qualitative data. The qualitative data was then applied to obtain background data which could be used as assumption values to cultivate samples calculations. The author requested foreground data of eco-social-economic aspects in the following fundamental categories:

- 1. Planet:**
 - a. Chemicals**
 - b. Transport**
 - c. Waste**
- 2. People**
 - a. Wages**
 - b. Child Labour**
- 3. Prosperity**
 - a. Corruption**

The questionnaire was sent to EMMASF, which was then further delivered to suppliers in their supply chain. Foreground data that could not be obtained through questionnaires and interviews, was substituted with background data using scientific literature sources, Life Cycle Analysis databases and lastly grey literature.

Based on unstructured interviews and meetings with various department professionals at EMMASF and Protag, it could be ascertained that the three components analysed in this research, namely; (1) leather ; (2) steel and (3) Polyurethane were purchased from Brazil, China and Germany respectively. EMMASF is purchasing 80% or more of its leather from Brazil from a long-term supplier. The supplier in turn has established a permanent relationship with the slaughterhouse by becoming a shareholder, in order to guarantee a continuous supply of raw leather, however, EMMASF does not know the level of relationship between the slaughterhouse and the farmer. The steel toe cap is supplied by long-term Chinese supplier and the steel outsole by a long term supplier in Brazil. The materials for the PU midsoles are supplied by Covestro¹⁴ in Germany. The final assembly of the PU components are manufactured in Protag, EMMASF's production location in Brunssum, The Netherlands.

¹³ Appendix 2

¹⁴ <https://www.covestro.com/en>

To determine the impact of the Oiconomy Standard approach, this research assumes 5 types of supply chains for the Article 730 D Billy. In each supply chain, three main components of the leather safety shoe and the production process at Protag are considered. The 5 supply chains¹⁵ are divided into the following:

1. Conventional Supply Chain (currently used by EMMASF)
2. Circular Supply Chain (recently developed by EMMASF)
3. European Supply Chain (future goal of EMMASF to bring all production back to Europe)
4. BRIC Supply Chain (assuming the worst case scenario)
5. New Markets Supply Chain (assuming expansion into unknown territories)

The above supply chains are realistic in the field of leather safety footwear and therefore this research will calculate the preventive cost in each supply chain. Subsequently, each PPP category will be examined to analyse the actions that could be taken to prevent negative impact in the future.

Protag is the EMMASF product location in The Netherlands and it is assumed that EMMASF follows EU regulations with regards to chemicals and hazardous chemicals. During a site visit and interview with production managers, the author noted that hazardous chemicals are regarded with care and stored separately and away from the main factory area. In this case, no ESCU'S need to be allocated. The ESCU's for transport is the distance between Protag and the customer, in this case, ENGIE Services located in Bunnik, The Netherlands. The least efficient means by truck was assumed. The ESCU'S for wages, child labour and corruption are nil as it is again assumed that EU regulations apply to these categories.

Calculations were made using the Oiconomy data-sheet [O.F.- database], which lists the ESCU factors for each issue (version 17.06.01 available for download via Utrecht University, 2018). To understand in more detail the nature of data that was collected and how this data was used to calculate the ESCUs for each criteria, will be explained in the following paragraphs. Calculations were made using the Oiconomy data-sheet [O.F.- database], which lists the ESCU factors for each issue (version 17.06.01 available for download via Utrecht University, 2018). Additionally, with the aim of outlining the production process of a leather safety shoe, assumptions have been made to define the route these processes take. The following subsections will explain how the calculations were made per PPP category, as well as describing which assumptions have been made.

4.3.1 Planet

For the purpose of this research the environmental impact on the Planet is determined by the pollution of water by chemicals, transport of goods from supplier to consumer and the waste in relation to the component (leather, steel, polyurethane).

¹⁵ Appendix 3

4.3.1.1. Chemicals

Leather

According to REACH regulations (May 2015)¹⁶, the only chromium VI restriction applicable to leather was for its use in personal protective equipment (PPE). The restriction in REACH Annex XVII relating to chromium VI has been extended to include leather articles or leather parts of articles that come into contact with the skin. The maximum amount of chromium VI must be below 3mg/kg (0.0003 per cent) of the total dry weight of leather. This concentration is the detection limit of International Standards Organisation EN ISO 17075¹⁷ – the only internationally recognized analytical method currently available to detect chromium VI in leather (REACH). Water contamination from leather tanning releases relatively large amounts of chromium in surface waters where it can stay for many years. The negative side of the chromium is that it forms Cr (VI) in various stages of leather processing which is carcinogenic (Kanagaraj et al., 2007). The ESCU for pollution of water by chemicals is ESCU per kilogram.

The calculation:

ESCU = ESCU per kgs * chemical substance percentage per kg

ESCU = Chromium VI * ESCU per kg

Chromium VI: weight of chromium in 1 kg of leather

Steel Toe Cap and Outsole

Stainless steels generally contain between 10-20% chromium as the main alloying element (Greenpeace, 2018). Steel production has a number of impacts on the environment including wastewater contaminants, hazardous wastes, and solid wastes. The major environmental impacts from integrated steel mills are from coking and iron-making. Assuming the worst case scenario, this research uses the maximum 20% chromium in steel. The impact on the environment through eutrophication in water is taken from existing databases (Vogtländer, IDEMATAPP2016_with_eco-costs_and_carbon_footprint). The maximum ESCU value to prevent negative impact has been assumed for all countries in the 5 supply chains.

The Calculation:

ESCU = ESCU per kgs * chemical substance percentage per kg

ESCU = Chromium in air* ESCU per kg

Chromium in 0,173g steel = 0,173*20%

¹⁶ <https://echa.europa.eu/home>

¹⁷ <https://www.iso.org/home.html>

4.3.1.2. Transport

Transport was calculated using specific distances of each part of the journey for each component. The least efficient means of transport by truck and shipping vessel was assumed because some background data was used to make the calculation. To calculate the actual distance between factory and port, port to port, port to production location, production location to distributor, google maps was used.

Leather, Steel Toe Cap & Outsole, Polyurethane Midsole

To calculate the ESCU'S for transport, the component weight in relation to the shoe must be determined. Using foreground data from a materials overview¹⁸ from EMMASF, the component weight could be determined. Then the distance is calculated using google maps and the t.km was calculated by the following equation.

The Calculation:

$$\text{ESCU} = \text{Shipped weight (kg)} * \text{distance km} / 1000$$

4.3.1.3. Waste

Leather

The leather industry generates 0.7 kg / kg of solid waste from processed hides and skins (Sekaran et al, 2007). The waste in leather is derived mainly from buffing dust, shavings and sludge causing contamination in water. The ESCU per kg is taken from existing databases (Vogtländer, IDEMATAPP2016_with_eco-costs_and_carbon_footprint). The ESCU for waste is applied in all 5 supply chains.

The Calculation:

$$\text{ESCU} = \text{ESCU per kg} + \text{Waste per kg.}$$

Steel Toe cap and Outsole

Alloy Steel mainly contain added metals, such as manganese (hardness), nickel (strength), molybdenum (improved wear), tungsten (high temperature strength), chromium (corrosion resistance), and vanadium (toughness). The limestone and iron ore impurities collected at the top of the molten iron, make up the largest portion of iron-making waste/by-products. While this is not a pollution prevention technique, the solid waste does not reach landfills.(Greenpeace). Steel is 100% recyclable

¹⁸ Table 1

and therefore it is assumed that the waste in the supply chains of EMMASF will not reach landfill. The ESCU is set at nil.

ESCU Outcomes for Category Planet

The following section demonstrates some of the potential outcomes of the calculations. For chemicals, the ESCU value for chromium in water is presented. For transport, the total ESCU value for the three components in the 5 different supply chains are presented. Finally, the total ESCU value for Plant across the 5 supply chains are presented.

Chemicals

Figure 4 : ESCU's for Chromium in Water during Leather Tanning

Figure 4 above demonstrated the ESCU value for chromium pollution in water from salting the leather hides. The maximum value according to EU legislation of 3mg/kg (0.0003 per cent) is used to calculate the ESCU for pollution of water in India, The Netherlands and Ethiopia. Due to stringent EU regulations, the ESCU value is relatively low. The ESCU value in Brazil is nil because the tannery has an effluent plant treatment system (Questionnaire, Viposa, 2018). Further, the raw hides are not salted (Interview, Ronny van der Wegen, 2018) and therefore chromium is not formed.

Figure 5 : Comparison of ESCU's for Transport across the 5 supply chains

Figure 5 above shows the ESCU value needed to prevent negative impact in each supply chain for the sum of the components, leather, steel and polyurethane. BRIC shows the highest value, while Conventional and Circular are identical. Considering that the distance in each supply chain will not change, it can be deduced that if EMMASF use exactly the same suppliers for their Conventional and Circular supply chain, with the same routes, in effect the negative impact between these two supply chains is indistinguishable. New markets can be considered a better option for transport, but overall it is clear that the transport ESCU's in the EU supply chain have the least negative impact.

Figure 6 : Comparison of total ESCU's for Planet across the 5 supply chains

Figure 6 above explains the ESCU value of 63,29% of the total components of the leather safety shoe 730 D Billy. The conventional and circular supply chains are equivalent to each other because the processes in these two supply chains are identical. The worst case scenario is represented by the BRIC supply chain and the best case scenario is represented by the EU supply chain.

4.3.2. People

For the purpose of this research the social impact categories for People is weighted by Wages and Child Labour. To avoid double counting, it is assumed that in countries where risk of child labour is high, the ESCU for child labour is counted as the preventive cost. In countries where child labour is strictly prohibited or where the supplier can prove there is no child labour, the ESCU for Wages is counted.

4.3.2.1. Wages

Croes (2012), states a difference between the legally set minimum wages and actual fair wages, because legal minimum wages are disparate from fair wages or living wages. The OS database [O.F.-04 Country Statements] lists the gross fair minimum wages (FMW) per country per year and per hour, based on data provided by the World Bank.

This research assumes that a business observes the legally set minimum wage set by local government. This implies that if the OS [O.F.-04 Country Statements] states that FMW and the legally minimum wage are the same, no ESCUs will be allocated. For example, the minimum legal wage in The Netherlands can be considered as a fair wage (FMW). This suggests that when the production facility of EMMASF, namely; Protag, is conforming to the legal wage requirements of the country, EMMASF/Protag remunerates their employees with a fair wage. In this case, no ESCU'S need to be allocated. However, in contrast, the minimum legal wage in low developed countries are not always equal to the FMW. To ascertain whether the suppliers in EMMASF supply chain conform to the legal minimum wage or to the FMW of the country they are located in, a questionnaire sent out¹⁹, requesting information on whether the minimum wage is paid or higher than the minimum wage. All questionnaires were returned with the answer that the legal minimum wage was paid. It can therefore be assumed that the suppliers in low developed countries do not comply with the FMW. FMW/h is given by the OS, LW/h is calculated by dividing LW with the maximum amount of working days as set by the OS which is 1,864 hours (Croes, 2012).

The Calculation:

ESCU's Fair Wage = (FMW/h – LW/h) * Working hours / safety shoe

FMW/h: Fair Minimum Wage per hour

LW/h: Legal minimum wage within country

Working hours / safety shoe: the amount of hours it takes to produce the safety shoe.

¹⁹ Appendix 2

4.3.2.2. Child Labour

The OS system states the ESCU score for child labor depends on two possible situations (Croes, 2012, p. 40):

If [O.F.-04 country statements] in the OS database demonstrates that within the country of the organization child labor is absent, or verification by a therefore accredited certification body, no ESCUs are allocated.

If [O.F.-04 country statements] indicates the risk of child labor within the country of the organization, and independently verified absence of child labor cannot be demonstrated, the organization has to state the amount of workhours necessary for the product. The Expected Labor Costs are calculated as the [Adult Fair Minimum Wage x Average Amount of Workhours]. The ESCUs are calculated as the [Expected Labor Costs – demonstrable, well registered labor payment, in accordance with product cost calculations] for the relevant work. At any doubt about the labor payment, it shall be considered zero. The ESCUs shall be calculated separately for labor acceptable according to [O.F.-20 Child Labor] except for their payment, and for other child labor, and added together. If an organization uses a group of not certified small suppliers in a country with child labor risk, according to [O.F.-04 country statements], such as workshops and home based workers, absence of child labor shall should be demonstrated by continuous audits.

EMMASF Product Managers and Product Developers report no cases of child labour have been witnessed. These assessments cannot be verified by industry auditing systems or certifications for social and/or environmental management. It is also unknown if these suppliers subcontract to smaller factories or other workshops. It can therefore be assumed that child labour may occur and therefore ESCU's need to be assigned. Child labour risk is high in low developed countries (Unicef 2018). The calculation used for determining child labour is fair minimum wage multiplied by the number of hours it takes to make a safety shoe.

The Calculation:

ESCU's Child Labour = FMW/h * Working hours / safety shoe

FMW/h: Fair Minimum Wage per hour

Working hours / safety shoe: the amount of hours it takes to produce the safety shoe

ESCU Outcomes for Category People

The following section demonstrates with graphs some of the outcomes for the category People, looking at ESCU's for child labour in low developed countries.

Child Labour

Figure 7 : The difference between the current FMW and the ESCU needed to prevent negative impact.

Figure 7 above demonstrates the ESCU's for child labour in India, China and Ethiopia. This research used background data to calculate the ESCU value in high risk countries. During the production phase, the status of labour can be assumed, meaning that this research makes an assumption on whether the product was produced by a worker of legal minimum age or by child labour. This research does not have enough evidence to calculate whether parts of the shoe was produced by legal labour or child labour. In countries where there is a high degree of child labour sensitive issues, we have assumed that the worst case scenario and taken the ESCU for child labour. If wages is not calculated in the total, it has been replaced by child labour for the calculation.

4.3.3. Prosperity

For the purpose of this research the societal impact category to be calculated is Corruption.

4.3.3.1. Corruption

OS uses the Corruption Perception Index (CPI)²⁰ as input to define the ESCU's for corruption. If the CPI of the country in which the organization operates is higher than 60, no ESCU's are allocated. The OS contains two additional matter, (1) whether money transfers occur with any other organization or private person that it has ownership relations with, in a country with a CPI below 60 and (2) whether the organization contributes to armed conflict. For the purpose of this research, neither are taken into account.

If the CPI of the country in which the organization is operating is lower than 60, additional research is required to determine the ESCUs. The OS makes use of a specific governance level scoring model [O.F.-23 Governance Level scoring model], based on a company assessment of Dreyer (et al., 2010) to assess the organization's governance level on corruption (Plan-Do-Check-Act). This model calculates the organization's governance score, which is used as a reducing "corruption factor" to be multiplied by the net operational product margin

This research uses the 5-year average net operational profit margin of the industry sector in the S&P 500 multiplied by the price of the product in the value chain.

The CPI score for the EU countries are:

1. Netherlands is 87
2. Germany is 81
3. United Kingdom is 81

These scores are above the CPI threshold of 60, which means no ESCUs for these countries need to be allocated. The ESCU value is therefore set at nil.

The CPI score for low developed countries in this research:

1. Brazil is 38
2. China is 37
3. India is 38
4. Ethiopia is 33
5. South Africa is 44
6. Russia is 29

²⁰ <https://www.transparency.org/>

These scores are below the CPI threshold of 60, which means that ESCUs must be calculated for these countries using the governance level scoring model and data on their net operational product margin. The OS stresses that this should be the 5-year average product margin, but as this research does not have access to that information, the 5-year average net operational profit margin of the industry sector in the S&P 500 is used. This formula is used in the sectors for leather and steel. For leather, the industry sector is Retail Apparel and for steel the industry sector is Iron and Steel. For Polyurethane, the sector Chemicals (plastic and rubber).

The Calculation:

$$\text{ESCU} = (\text{5 yr net margin}) * (\text{cost price of the product})$$

ESCU Outcomes for Category Prosperity

In this section, the calculations exhibit the cost of corruption in the different supply chains. The graphs below show (1) the difference between ESCU's in the 5 supply chains to mitigate corruption²¹ and (2) the difference between ESCU values for corruption in the leather supply chain in each country²².

Figure 8 : The difference in ESCU value between the 5 supply chains to mitigate corruption

²¹ Figure 8

²² Figure 9

Figure 8 above describes the difference in corruption in the diverse supply chains. For example in the conventional and circular supply chains, EMMASF procures its leather and steel from Brazil, so the corruption ESCU is the same in both these supply chains. In the BRIC supply chain, this research theorises that if the leather is procured from India, the steel from Brazil and the PU from China, the corruption ESCU increases substantially because all three countries have a CPI score that is less than 60. New markets supposes that if the leather is procured from Ethiopia and the steel from Russia, the corruption ESCU is also substantially high with both countries having CPI scores less than 60. The EU supply chain represent countries above the CPI threshold of 60, which means no ESCUs for these countries need to be allocated. The ESCU value is therefore set at nil.

Figure 9 : Difference in ESCU's for corruption in the leather supply chain per country

Figure 9 above illustrates the ESCU values for corruption specifically in the leather supply chain. Currently, EMMASF procures leather from Brazil and India. The 5 year average net margin of the sector Retail and Apparel was multiplied by the cost price of leather in each country with a CPI score < 60. The price of leather in India was the highest and therefore generated the highest corruption score. Ethiopia generated a score less than India but greater Brazil. The Netherlands CPI score is above the threshold of 60, which means no ESCUs for these countries need to be allocated. The ESCU value is therefore set at nil.

4.4. A Comparison between Case Study: Part One and Case Study: Part two

In this section, a comparison is made between the sustainability practises at EMMASF and the application of the OS method.

In 2016 EMMASF started a project to redesign safety footwear, with the intention to take their core products from linear to circular. In order to do this, the company contracted FFBasic, a consultancy firm, specialising in sustainability. FFBasic and EMMASF looked to C2C assessment criteria to motivate their evaluations of conventional safety shoes. Using C2C inspiration, they developed new models of safety footwear by categorising components of the safety shoe into a grading system denoting the level of recyclability. This is a qualitative measuring system and therefore numerical values are not assigned.

The OS incorporates the principles of standard financial accounting to determine the ESCUs of a product at all links in the supply chain. The ESCU transfers sustainability through the supply chain, in a normalized way that allows all supply chain players to build on each other's data (Croes, 2012). It can be observed that the four vertical tiers of the shoe production can be plotted in the supply chain. Within these four tiers, this research is limited to specific aspects; the three major components of the leather safety shoe: leather, steel and polyurethane. Further these components are subdivided into the three PPP categories; Planet (chemical, transport, waste), People (wages, child labour) and Prosperity (corruption) in the five diverse supply chains. Together with the standard (economic) price of the product, the ESCU score represents the total costs of a fully sustainable alternative for the product. With this, it becomes possible to know how sustainable the base-line product is, and what needs to be done in order to have a completely sustainable product (Croes, 2012). This is a quantifiable method and is represented in virtual monetary value, allowing the producer to assign an eco-cost value to the product in the supply chain.

5. Analysis & Discussion

On reflection, the main observation is that the discrepancy between the current monitoring and assessment practices at EMMASF and the Oiconomy standard is the difference between qualitative evaluation and quantitative evaluation. EMMASF employs the theory of C2C to develop circular products. In essence, C2C is a system that categorises components in A, B, C or X categories, to assess whether the component has next use phase. However, this method is not empirical and it is vastly unclear what the level of the quality of the component will be after being recycled and whether it can be used in safety shoes or in other applications. While C2C can be well applied in the design phase of a product, it does not evaluate the total circularity of the leather safety shoe and therefore cannot be considered to be contributing to the CE. While there are numerous definitions of CE, the general consensus is that CE moves away from a linear economy to transition to one that is circular.

The OS in comparison is an in-depth quantitative method that allows the user to calculate the actual preventative cost along the supply chain from raw material to post-consumer disposal. This quantitative method underscores the potential to link SSCM to circularity to fully incorporate CE principles in the

leather supply chain. The OS is an holistic approach, taking into account all phases of a product’s life cycle including Planet, People and Prosperity. The OS can contribute to giving a realistic overview to whether the leather safety shoe is circular in product and process. This pilot study applied the OS method to execute calculations on the main components of Article 730 D Billy; leather, steel and polyurethane. Further these components were analysed in three PPP categories and further delineated on country level. The calculations performed by the OS method revealed a lack of transparency and due diligence in the supply chain, which will be further explained in this chapter.

The first observation using the OS method is the differences between the retail price, the ESCU value, and the preventive costs of the product, demonstrated in Figure 10 below. With this calculation, the producer is able to identify eco-costs in each supply chain, and subsequently identify the total cost necessary to provide a sustainable alternative. The ESCU score equals the hidden costs of the product. These are the costs that should have been spent to avoid any of the damage that the product causes during its entire lifecycle. Together with the standard (economic) price of the product, the ESCU score represents the total costs of a fully sustainable alternative for the product.

Figure 10 The Real Cost (total escu + retail price) to achieve a fully sustainable product

The price of the Article 730 D Billy retails at €86,20 excluding value added tax²³. This is the price without the ESCU values. The total ESCU value is the amount that should be spent to prevent any of the damage

²³ <https://emmafootwear.nl/emma-billy-s3-werkschoen>

that the product causes during its entire lifecycle. This is the cost in euros that a company must outlay for production of a safety shoe to prevent negative impact. Finally, the sum of the ESCU value plus the retail price denote the total amount that should be spent to create a sustainable alternative.

The ESCU values for the conventional supply chain and the circular supply chain at EMMASF are exactly the same. Hence, the OS method brings to light the fact that if a company uses all the same materials and processes in the main components of a product, there is no difference between conventional production processes and circular production processes. Therefore, by definition, a product cannot be marketed as circular if all elements in relation to the product are not transparently accounted for. Further, the BRIC supply chain has the highest ESCU value and the New Markets supply chain the second highest. This demonstrates that the preventative costs in these supply chains will be the highest respectively. The lowest preventative cost are in the EU supply chain, which is advantageous only if the company moves all procurement and production to the European Union.

The second observation is that the ESCU values for Planet are relatively low in comparison to People and Prosperity. The difference in ESCU's is demonstrated in Figure 11 below.

Figure 11 : Comparison of ESCU's between Planet, People and Prosperity

In comparing the ESCU values for Planet, People and Prosperity, it is evident that the highest preventative cost lies in the category People, second highest is Prosperity however, unexpectedly the

ESCU values for Planet the lowest. Furthermore, the ESCU's for long distance transport²⁴ will not change. In fact, this research assumed shipping vessel and truck with an empty return, which can be assumed to having a lower impact than freight by air. Hence, the ESCU in reality could be higher, depending on the actual mode of transport used for the product at a given moment. It can therefore be established that while some ESCU's like emission by transport will be difficult to reduce, it has been identified that other ESCU's like wages, child labour and corruption is a matter of the company's relationship with the supplier and the actions taken together with the supplier to create solutions to improve these conditions.

This research looked at what suppliers need to do to get to zero impact. However, what is the meaning of these values and how can it be communicated to EMMASF? Simply, a very high value is based on the assumption that the producer does not perform due diligence in their supply chain and therefore the most expensive preventive measure has been calculated. The message to EMMASF is that if they do perform due diligence in their supply, then probably for less than anticipated, the negative impact can be removed. To elaborate further, what can be derived from the analysis of the calculation is that if a producer were to take the worst case scenario like the BRIC supply chain, the total preventative cost is what the producer would need to outlay financially to prevent negative impact. Accordingly, in the Brazil part of the supply chain, for the leather, the categories that include technical investments in production facilities like recalibrating prevention methods for pollution in water and waste, eventually not only lower the environmental impact, but also increase the level of social sustainability by improving safety and health issues alongside, creating value for people in the low developed countries. In retrospect, a comparison of the current monitoring at EMMASF and the new innovative OS method reveal the difference between qualitative and quantitative measure. The next step could be to look for potential preventative activities that in this industry; for example; to use assessments like Tannery of the Future and then recalculate what the impact of an improved leather safety shoe would be, based on the requirements of these initial qualitative assessments.

Reflecting on the use of the OS method for this research, it should be noted that this was a pilot study and the application of the OS method was exploratory. The author had not worked with this method previously. One of the challenges of the OS method is that it is a method that assumes suppliers and producers are working collaboratively, however, this is the most problematic fragment of gathering data, because it was a mammoth challenge to encourage and coax supply chain partners to work together to provide relevant and accurate data. Nonetheless, wherever foreground data was not available, it was nonetheless possible to use the OS method with background data to calculate what the preventive cost might look like in the supply chain. Henceforth, providing industry relevant background data is a step that can be further elaborated on in the OS method.

The OS method, for practical purposes, is not yet user friendly for corporate responsibility (CR) managers as it stands. This innovative performance measurement system can become more user friendly by developing a template that CR managers, including a spread sheet with formulas per industry. An easy step by step explanation is necessary for the industries to understand how beneficial these quantitative calculations can be in identifying sustainability issues in the supply chain. There are

²⁴ Figure 5

possible alternatives to the current assumptions in the system, for example, the manner in which this research captured and utilised background data could be used for the OS method to map SD issues, consequently appropriating international data sources which can be used to perform preliminary calculations. Hence, the next step for the OS method may be to do a systematic analysis of available industry specific background data sources. Finally, the OS method needs to develop easily assessable guidelines on how to manage expectations when using the system.

Irrespective of the limitations in this research, which only considers 63,29% of the total components of the leather safety shoe, the difference between qualitative and quantitative measurement can be compared. In an analysis of what measurement systems are being applied currently at EMMASF in the section Cast Study: Part 1, it can be deduced that the measurement system is qualitative and speculative because the company is looking at sustainability options but not looking at what is actually being done to improve sustainability in the supply chains they work with. Contrary to qualitative measurement systems, the OS quantifies with a numerical value what needs to be done to reach a fully sustainable product. While the application of the OS is limited to a specific number of sustainability aspects and only three major components of the safety shoe, the OS nonetheless still gives a verifiable method on how to calculate the (un)sustainability of a leather safety shoe.

6. Recommendations

The recommendations for further application of the OS method for businesses and in this case, EMMASF, is to experiment with this quantitative method, and use it to create openness and additional collaboration in the supply chain. The OS method can allow businesses to identify where improvements could be made. The OS method can be used to calculate the level of due diligence in the supply chain, thereby creating a higher level of transparency. Creating transparency in turn minimises the ESCU because the producer is in control of their supply chain. This analysis could be used to jointly identify the key points for improvement because it focuses on the preventative actions. The next key steps for EMMASF would be to perform critical due diligence in their various supply chains, collecting measureable information with regards to planet, people and prosperity issues and applying the OS method. Since the leather supply chain is an important supply chain in the totality of the safety shoe, it would be beneficial for all the actors in this supply chain to apply the OS method, in order to quantify how (un)sustainable they are and at what level of circularity are their products and processes.

The recommendations for the industry at large is for initiatives like Tannery of the Future to link their proposals on the improvements of production conditions to indicate measurement in calculating ESCU values. This tool can be used to discover what steps are needed to improve leather production, while the OS method can quantify these steps.

The recommendations for scientific research would be to improve cost based assessments. The OS method approaches the supply chain from the end producer. Since it difficult to access data and requires the end producer to track data to be able to make a calculation, a solution could be to start at the beginning of the supply at the raw materials phase, subsequently moving up the supply chain. Further research in the leather supply chain should include animal welfare and the allocation of emissions for leather as a by-product.

7. Conclusion

The objective of this research was to demonstrate how negative environmental and social impacts along the value chain can be controlled and eventually eliminated by applying a fully integrated performance measurement system. To answer the research question, *“How can the application of a quantitative performance measurement system, lead to a valid cost-benefit analysis, to improve the sustainability performance of the product (leather safety shoe) through comparing supply chain alternatives?”* this research thesis conducted a two part case study, the current sustainability practise at EMMASF and an alternative case study using the OS method. Further, to determine the validity of such a performance measurement system, an evaluation of the current assessment method applied by the producer was conducted, thereby answering the sub-question: *“What performance measurement system approaches are being currently employed by the producer?”* The overall conclusion that can be derived is that there are clear differences between the two approaches in the level of specificity and how EMMASF utilises foreground information. The OS method proves to be more conclusive because it is able to address the PPP aspects in terms of what should be done and more importantly provides quantification in addressing the financial costs necessary to prevent negative impacts.

This was a case study with an embedded pilot study so the author made choices on which PPP aspects to cover, meaning that not all aspects have been covered. In environmental responsibility the research focused on chemicals, transport and waste; in social responsibility categories covered were wages and child labour; and in societal prosperity the category covered one aspect, namely; corruption. There are many more aspects that need to be covered to gain a comprehensive view of the supply chain. A preliminary conclusion that can be drawn it that there is still much work to be done in social sustainability to ensure global fairness in the supply chain. This research only looked at wages and child labour in the category People, however, it would be more thought-provoking to take into account other issues like safety, health and occupation and gender equality to name a few. Social sustainability is about welfare transfer from north to south, because the global north is predominantly producing goods in the global south, where there is a great disparity between the actual fair wage and the local minimum wage. This same reasoning accounts for environmental sustainability. The research only looked at chromium in leather, chromium in steel, the transport costs in the category Planet, though, it would be far more relevant to define all hazardous chemicals, waste and transport emissions for all the components in the five different supply chains. Quantifying these negative impacts will allow the company to identify their next steps in communicating sustainable strategy with supply chain partners.

Further, it can be concluded that the added value of the quantitative information of the OS method provides clear evidence about the impacts of strategic value chain choices in the overall strategy of the company. Their current strategy to move production back to Europe proves to be positive in the sense of reducing the ESCUs, while alternatives of continuing in unbeaten areas like the BRIC Supply Chain or New Markets is not tactical if they want to reduce negative impacts in the supply chain. However, it should also be noted that the high ESCU values present in less sustainable supply chains demonstrates a lack of due diligence in their partner supply chains, but, if they can contribute to improving social and environmental conditions in these less sustainable supply chains, the company can demonstrate a

massive impact in reducing negative impact in all three PPP categories. This ensures a healthy global supply chain which supports prosperity in the global south.

At face value, the first response is that this outcome is negative for the supply chain of the brand, but it can also be considered that if the research uses international data sources to incorporate the best information possible thereby extracting a valid reasoning then it can also be assumed that the approach used to calculate the (un)sustainability of a product is valid. Even though the foreground data is incomplete, this research gives a realistic view on sustainability in the supply chain. The challenge for every high ESCU value is to eliminate uncertainty with regards to environmental and social impact in the global supply chain of the company. The OS method calculation provides the reasoning to proactively open discussion on global fairness issues like raising wages, improving labour conditions, ensuring gender quality, guaranteeing health and safety, and many others. Similarly, low ESCU values means that in the communication with the supply chain, only a few steps need to be implemented for change to occur and reach zero impact.

Finally, the OS gives detailed information about which supply chains are more beneficial for EMMASF in the future. This quantitative data contributes to the business strategy of EMMASF to move production to Europe, as one of the company's long-term goals. The OS method shows that bringing back production to Europe generates a high level of sustainability of the EMMASF leather safety shoe, thereby confirming the company's sustainable business strategy.

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Appendix

Appendix 1

Interviews & Personal Communication

Company Name	Interviewee	Subject of Interview	Date
EMMA Safety Footwear	Paul Smetsers	Product Development	11-10-2017
EMMA Safety Footwear	Chantal Kerckhof	Financial Controller Assistant	30-11-2017
EMMA Safety Footwear	Hennie Emmerink	Financial Assistant	30-11-2017
FB Basic	Frans Beckers	Current assessment and monitoring processes	23-11-2017
FB Basic	Frans Beckers	PDS & MSDS viewing	07-12-2017
EMMA Safety Footwear	Chantal Kerckhof	Financial Controller Assistant	
EMMA safety Footwear	Frans Moonen	Product Engineer	20-12-2017
EMMA Safety Footwear	Jo Ruypers	Buyer	20-12-2017
EMMA Safety Footwear	Leon Visker	Quality Control	20-12-2017
EMMA Safety Footwear	Ronny van der Wegen	Supply Chain Management	07-02-2018
EMMA Safety Footwear	Iris van Wanrooij	Programme Manager Sustainability	27-03-2018
Tannery of the Future	Frans Tilstra	Performance Tools in the Leather Supply Chain	12-04-2018

Appendix 2

Data Collection - First Questionnaire

First Questionnaire	
Category	Question
Planet	
Air Pollution	1. Are all relevant activities standard in the sector and sector emissions per unit known? If yes, the sector data may be used, referring to the relevant data sources. Please provide your sources.
	2. Which internal qualified person is responsible for the data and what are her/his qualifications?
	3. Is the energy supplier certified?
	4. Can you list for each type of transport means the yearly km's of transport of people used in relation to the product?
	5. Can you list for each type of transport means the yearly tonkm's of transport of goods used in relation to the product?
	6. Can you list the activity/activities related to the product causes indirect gas emissions?
Depletion	1. What method do you use to determine the depletion of scarce resources (minerals, plant materials, animal materials)?
	2. What is the quantity of used water in relation to the product and the costs of purchasing that quantity (if purchased)?
	3. Is water purchased from a supplier?
Land Occupation	1. What is the size of the occupied piece of land, used for the product. (unused parts shall be divided over products proportionally to used surfaces)?
	2. Does your organization has an approved certificate on the product?
	3. What is the size of the occupied piece of land for the livestock and self-grown grass and feedstuffs?
Disposal and Waste	1. Waste quantities - List all quantities of waste from the materials related to the product, with the (yearly) average prices obtained or paid for it.
	2. Traceability - Describe, with evidence for each quantity of waste material, the end destination as: "reuse", "recycling", "incineration", "landfill", or else as "unknown".
	3. Foreign destinations - Describe for foreign destinations of waste, if the export is sustainable (returned to a certified upstream supplier, or traceable until recycled)
Animal Welfare	1. What are the company's policies on animal welfare?
	2. Are your partner tanneries certified?
	3. Does the company have a plan of action to improve conditions for animal welfare?
People	
Fair Wages	1. What are the lowest incomes paid in the organization related to the product, including those by contractors and self-employed workers?
	2. What are the highest yearly gross remuneration including bonuses and other benefits?
	3. What is the company policy on overwork wages?
Insurance	1. Does the company provide a pension plan? If so, what is the policy?
	2. Does the company provide health insurance to workers?
Code of Conduct	1. Does the company have a Code of Conduct for social and labour convergence?

Data Collection - Second Questionnaire

Second Questionnaire	
Category	Question
Planet	
Air Pollution	1. Has your facility documented it's air-emissions for: a. Greenhouse Gases b. Acidificaton c. Eutrication d. Ecotoxicity e. Fine dust
	2. Do you have a maintenance programme or cleaning schedule for improvement? a. Yes b. No
	3. Do you measure the air quality in your buildings? a. Yes b. No
Transport	1. Can you give for each type of transport means the yearly km's of transport of people used in relation to the product: a. Bus b. Train c. Plane d. Truck
	2. Can you give for each type of transport means the yearly ton km's of transport of goods used in relation to the product? a. Bus b. Train c. Plane d. Truck
Water Management	1. Do you measure the volume of water you are consuming? A. Yes b. No
	2. Do you measure the quality level of the water? A. Yes b. No
	3. What measures do you take to reduce usage of water? Please explain in detail.
	4. How do you ensure that polluted water does not contaminate your surrounding environment? Please explain in detail.
	5. Does your facility make use of a functioning effluent treatment system on a regular basis? If yes, please provide more information.
Waste Management	1. Do you take measures to reduce waste in your tannery/production location? Yes - Please describe your methods No - What is your plan of action?
	2. Do you take measures to recycle waste in your tannery/production facility? Yes - Please describe your methods No - What is your plan of action?
	3. Do you have dedicated ways to deal with: Fleshings? Lime waste? shavings? trimmings?
	4. What measures do you take to prevent chemical spills ending up in the environment? Please explain.
	5. Do you segregate waste streams in order to allow for the recycling of certain waste streams? Yes No
	6. Waste quantities - List all quantities of waste from the materials related to the product, with the (yearly) average prices obtained or paid for it.
	7. Describe, with evidence for each quantity of waste material, the end destination as: "reuse", "recycling", "incineration", "landfill", or else as "unknown".
Animal Welfare	1. What are the company's policies on animal welfare with regards to: a. Rearing b. Transportation c. Slaughter standards
	2. Does your company have a plan of action to improve conditions for animal welfare?

People	
Health & Safety	1. Do you organise Health and Safety training for workers? a. Yes b. No
	2. Do you measure the formation and occurrence of: a. Hydrogen sulphide Yes / No b. Chrome VI Yes / No
	3. Do you take steps to prevent workers from coming into contact with: a. Formaldehyde Yes / No b. Hydrogen sulphide Yes / No c. Chrome VI Yes / No
	4. Do the workers know how to handle a chemical spill? Yes / No
Gender Equality	5. Do the workers use the following Personal Protection Equipment (PPE)? a. Shoes-Boots Yes / No b. Gloves Yes / No c. Protective clothing Yes / No d. Chemical masks Yes / No e. Goggles Yes / No f. Earplugs for noisy areas Yes / No
	1. What is the ratio of male to female workers? a. Yes b. No
	2. Do female workers receive the same growth opportunity as male workers? a. Yes b. No
Wages	3. Do you pay female workers the same as male workers for the same function? a. Yes b. No
	1. Do you pay the minimum wage as set by the government? Yes / No a. If you pay a living wage, please clarify
	2. Are pregnant women entitled to maternity leave and benefits? a. Yes b. No
	3. Do you provide permanent contracts to all workers who do permanent work? a. Yes b. No
	4. What is the company policy on overwork wages? a. Yes b. No
	5. Does the company provide a pension plan? If so, what is the policy? a. Yes b. No
	6. Does the company provide health insurance to workers? a. Yes b. No
7. Does the company have a Code of Conduct for social and labour convergence? a. Yes b. No	
Prosperity	
Ethical Business	1. Did you acquire the land for your tannery without any undue payment to government officials and in a way that did not involve people's forced eviction from their land? Yes / No
	2. Have you been sure not to offer, promise, give, request, agree to or accept undue financial or any other advantages to or from public officials, or the workers of business partners? Yes / No
	3. Do you pay a fair level of tax (i.e., no tax evasion through agreements with governments, subsidies, loopholes, use of tax havens, creative accounting practices or transfer-pricing)? Yes / No
	4. Do you allow fair competition between yourself and your competitors? Yes / No
Sustainable Development	1. What is your program for sustainable development: a. Within your organisation? b. Towards your community at large?

Appendix 3 - Calculations

Supply Chain Overview with ESCU's

SUPPLY CHAIN OVERVIEW WITH ESCU's							
Conventional Safety Boot Supply chain (EMMA)							
Category	Planet			People		Prosperity	TOTAL
	Chemicals	Transport	Waste	Wages	Child Labour	Corruption	
LEATHER							
Brazil	€ 0,00	€ 1,84	€ 1,10	€ 24,87	€ 0,00	€ 7,42	€ 35,23
STEEL TOE CAP & OUTSOLE							
Brazil	€ 0,06	€ 2,39	€ 0,00	€ 24,87	€ 0,00	€ 2,19	€ 29,51
PU MIDSOLE							
Germany	€ 0,00	€ 0,02	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,02
PROTAG PRODUCTION							
The Netherlands	€ 0,00	€ 0,14	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,14
TOTAL ESCU							€ 64,90

Circular Safety Boot Supply Chain (EMMA)							
Category	Planet			People		Prosperity	TOTAL
	Chemicals	Transport	Waste	Wages	Child Labour	Corruption	
LEATHER							
Brazil	€ 0,00	1,84	€ 1,10	24,87	€ 0,00	€ 7,42	€ 35,23
STEEL TOE CAP & OUTSOLE							
Brazil	€ 0,06	2,39	€ 0,00	24,87	€ 0,00	€ 2,19	€ 29,51
PU MIDSOLE							
Germany	€ 0,00	0,02	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,02
PROTAG PRODUCTION							
The Netherlands	€ 0,00	€ 0,14	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,14
TOTAL ESCU							€ 64,90

BRIC Supply Chain							
Category	Planet			People		Prosperity	TOTAL
	Chemicals	Transport	Waste	Wages	Child Labour	Corruption	
LEATHER							
India	€ 0,04	€ 1,13	€ 1,10	€ 0,00	€ 8,96	€ 33,63	€ 44,86
STEEL TOE CAP & OUTSOLE							
Brazil	€ 0,06	€ 2,39	€ 0,00	€ 24,87	€ 0,00	€ 2,19	€ 29,51
PU MIDSOLE							
China	€ 0,00	€ 3,17	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 21,12	€ 2,19	€ 26,48
PROTAG PRODUCTION							
The Netherlands	€ 0,00	€ 0,14	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,14
TOTAL ESCU							€ 100,99

EU Supply Chain							
Category	Planet			People		Prosperity	TOTAL
	Chemicals	Transport	Waste	Wages	Child Labour	Corruption	
LEATHER							
The Netherlands	€ 0,04	€ 0,02	€ 1,10	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 1,16
STEEL TOE CAP & OUTSOLE							
Italy	€ 0,06	€ 0,18	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,24
PU MIDSOLE							
Germany	€ 0,00	€ 0,02	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,02
PROTAG PRODUCTION							
The Netherlands	€ 0,00	€ 0,14	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,14
TOTAL ESCU							€ 1,56

New Markets Supply Chain							
Category	Planet			People		Prosperity	TOTAL
	Chemicals	Transport	Waste	Wages	Child Labour	Corruption	
LEATHER							
Ethiopia	€ 0,04	€ 0,88	€ 1,10	€ 0,00	€ 8,64	€ 25,30	€ 35,96
STEEL TOE CAP & OUTSOLE							
Russia	€ 0,06	€ 0,42	€ 0,00	€ 38,71	€ 0,00	€ 2,19	€ 41,38
PU MIDSOLE							
Germany	€ 0,00	€ 0,02	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,02
PROTAG PRODUCTION							
The Netherlands	€ 0,00	€ 0,14	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,14
TOTAL ESCU							€ 77,50

Calculation Chemicals

CALCULATION CHEMICALS		
ESCU = ESCU per kgs * chemical substance percentage per kg		
LEATHER	Chromium VI in water	149,6
	Chromium % in 1 kg leather	0,0003
	ESCU	€ 0,04
	TOTAL ESCU	€ 0,04
STEEL	Chromium in Air	1,8381
	Chromium in 0,173g steel	0,0346
	ESCU	€ 0,06
	TOTAL ESCU	€ 0,06

Calculation Transport

		CALCULATION TRANSPORT					
		<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;"> ESCU = Shipped weight (kg) * distance km / 1000 </div>					
		<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;"> Distribution from Protag to Consumer (ENGIE) Distance from Protag Brunsum to ENGIE Bunnik 174 Weight of shoe 0,782 ESCU € 0,14 </div>					
LEATHER component weight KG	0,138	<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;"> Leather from Brazil to Protag 1st leg - Distance from factory to Rio port 1132 Weight of leather 0,138 ESCU € 0,16 2nd leg - Distance from Rio port to Rotterdam port 12038 Weight of leather 0,138 ESCU € 1,66 3rd leg - Rotterdam Port to Protag 193 Weight of leather 0,138 ESCU € 0,03 TOTAL ESCU € 1,84 </div>		<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;"> Leather from India to Protag 1st leg - Distance from factory to Chennai port 16,5 Weight of leather 0,138 ESCU € 0,00 2nd leg - Distance from Chennai port to Rotterdam port 7948 Weight of leather 0,138 ESCU € 1,10 3rd leg - Rotterdam Port to Protag 193 Weight of leather 0,138 ESCU € 0,03 TOTAL ESCU € 1,13 </div>			
		<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;"> Leather from Ehtipia to Protag 1st leg - Distance from factory to Djibouti port 813 Weight of leather 0,138 ESCU € 0,11 2nd leg - Distance from Djibouti port to Rotterdam port 5398 Weight of leather 0,138 ESCU € 0,74 3rd leg - Rotterdam port to Protag 193 Weight of leather 0,138 ESCU € 0,03 TOTAL ESCU € 0,88 </div>		<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;"> Leather from Rijen (NL) to Protag Distance from factory to Protag 145 Weight of leather 0,138 ESCU € 0,02 TOTAL ESCU € 0,02 </div>			
		<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;"> Steel from Brazil to Protag 1st leg - Distance from factory to Rio port 1580 Weight of steel 0,173 ESCU € 0,27 2nd leg - Distance from Rio port to Rotterdam port 12038 Weight of steel 0,173 ESCU € 2,08 3rd leg - Rotterdam port to Protag 193 Weight of steel 0,173 ESCU € 0,03 TOTAL ESCU € 2,39 </div>		<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;"> Steel from Italy Distance from factory to Protag 1024 Weight of steel 0,173 ESCU € 0,18 TOTAL ESCU € 0,18 </div>			
		<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;"> Steel from Russia Distance from factory to Protag 2422 Weight of steel 0,173 ESCU € 0,42 TOTAL ESCU € 0,42 </div>					
		POLYURETHANE MIDSOLE component weight	0,17	<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;"> PU from China 1st leg - Distance from factory to Xiamen port 18,4 Weight of PU 0,17 ESCU € 0,00 2nd leg - Distance from Xiamen port to Rotterdam port 18410 Weight of PU 0,17 ESCU € 3,13 3rd leg - Distance from Rotterdam port to Protag 193 Weight of PU 0,17 ESCU € 0,03 TOTAL ESCU € 3,17 </div>		<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;"> PU from Germany Distance from factory to Protag 101 Weight of PU 0,17 ESCU € 0,02 TOTAL ESCU € 0,02 </div>	

Calculation Waste

CALCULATION WASTE	
ESCU = ESCU per kg + Waste per kg	
LEATHER	Waste per kg 0,7
	Escu per kg 0,4
	ESCU € 1,10
	TOTAL ESCU € 1,10

Calculation Wages

CALCULATION WAGES		
ESCU = (FMW/h – LW/h) * Working hours per safety shoe		LW = LW per hour / 1864
		Working hours = 8
BRAZIL	LW	0,000805
	FMW	3,11
	ESCU	€ 24,87
	TOTAL ESCU	€ 24,87
RUSSIA	LW	0,000874
	FMW	4,84
	ESCU	€ 38,71
	TOTAL ESCU	€ 38,71

Calculation Child Labour

CALCULATION CHILD LABOUR		
ESCU - FMW * Working hours per safety shoe		
INDIA	FMW	1,12
	working hours per shoe	8
	ESCU	8,96
CHINA	FMW	2,64
	working hours per shoe	8
	ESCU	21,12
ETHIOPIA	FMW	1,08
	working hours per shoe	8
	ESCU	8,64

Calculation Corruption

CALCULATION CORRUPTION			
$\text{ESCU} = (5 \text{ yr net margin}) * (\text{cost price of the product})$			
LEATHER	BRAZIL	5 yr net margin	8,94
		Cost price of leather	0,83
		ESCU	€ 7,42
	INDIA	5 yr net margin	8,94
		Cost price of leather	3,76
		ESCU	€ 33,63
	ETHIOPIA	5 yr net margin	8,94
		Cost price of leather	2,83
		ESCU	€ 25,30
STEEL	BRAZIL	5 yr net margin	2,49
		Cost price of steel	0,88
		ESCU	€ 2,19
	CHINA	5 yr net margin	2,49
		Cost price of steel	0,88
		ESCU	€ 2,19
	RUSSIA	5 yr net margin	2,49
		Cost price of steel	0,88
		ESCU	€ 2,19